

Ich schwöre beim Schöpfer von Hoyda

(Ich schwöre bei der Welt der Materie und ihrer Grundlage)

(Identity impression)

Investigating the principles of Spencerism and survival conflict against hereditary Lamarckism and its symmetry with Darwin's theory

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Abstract:

According to many researchers, such as Weisman, Wallace, Bird, etc., the approach attributed to Darwin is at the opposite point of Lamarck's approach, and Lamarck's attitude is invalid, and its completion with the emergence of genetic theory, the strength of this attitude increased. But it should be noted that Lamarck's theory was not properly understood and Cuvier's opposition to him and his revolutionary attitude worsened this issue. Secondly, despite Darwin's clarification of his opposition to Lamarck, this disagreement can be partly related to his misunderstanding of Lamarck. Even in spite of this opposition, because of the objections to heredity mixed with the inheritance of acquired characteristics - henceforth Lamarck, he had become inclined. This attitude of neo-Darwinism is an extension of Darwin, and at the same time, it is unacceptable to consider Lamarckism's revival based on the achievements of molecular cell biology as a illusory attempt. Because the path traveled between Lamarck's initial idea to the formation of its later versions and the emergence of neo-Lamarckian attitudes and adherence to epigenetic phenomena can be explained under a main stream and under Lamarck's principles. By the way, although Lamarck did not know about genes and epigenes, he could provide a description of how the environment influences and the occurrence of inheritance of acquired characteristics, which is worthy of consideration despite all the problems it has.

Key words: Spencer-Lamarck-Darwin-Darwinism-Spencerism-Lamarckism-gene

Introduction:

At the beginning of the 19th century, Lamarck came to the conclusion that animate and inanimate beings are all products of nature and nature creates some directly and others indirectly. His main claim was that: nature can create only the simplest creatures in the manner of creation. These organisms become more complex animals and plants by changing the environmental and internal conditions and with the passage of time. As a result, these creatures have been produced indirectly by nature. By the way, Lamarck takes a fundamental step in rejecting the theory of the stability of species. By abandoning the idea of descent, he presented the first version of his theory about the transformation and transformation of living organisms. The

philosophy of zoology a few years later, Lamarck gave a more detailed explanation of how to disprove the theory of the stability of species in book 3 and presented the structure of the evolution of species in more detail. According to him, the species can maintain their shape only as long as their environment remains constant, and any change in the environment leads to a corresponding change in the species. In his defenses, he mentions domesticated animals and cultivated plants and the changes in their habits as examples, which have undergone a change due to the change in the environment. Lamarck, evolution can create every sin with his creations, the Supreme Creator of the world, "he does not consider sins as non-existent creations, and he believes that if he can certainly create one or two species for the creatures and give them the ability to evolve and change into other species to give Lamarck's description of how organisms adapt to nature and change species was in conflict with the issue of the ladder of life and its progress. This description of his by itself could not guarantee the linear order of the ladder of nature that he believed in and used in the theory of the classification of living things, and as a result, the evolution of animals could not have a progressing process.

Therefore, in order to solve the problem of the continuity of the ladder of nature and its incremental order, Lamarck inevitably started a new conceptualization in the theoretical field and used concepts such as progress, which were mainly raised in goal-oriented philosophies, in a new way about animals, and finally, the concept of complexity by using the concept presented heat (caloric fluid) and the external and internal movement of fluids. In fact, Lamarck's evolutionary system has two parts: the first part is related to the environment and adaptation, with which he proves the theory of species change, and the second part is about the issue of progress and according to Hebandi theorizes to defend the historical orientation of natural philosophy and the arrangement of beings from simple to complex. Another force that laterally shapes the sub-branches of the tree of life and shows how environmental factors can act locally, against the direction of progress.

Herbert Spencer

Herbert Spencer is one of the greatest philosophers of the 19th century. He was born in 1820. His father and grandfather were teachers and he himself was interested in mathematics and technical sciences while studying and studied engineering. But he did not have a regular and methodical education and obtained his abundant and

scattered information through personal experience and observations. Spencer, a materialist, was a brewer in his time with Karl Marx. He also believed in social segregation. Herbert Spencer was born on April 27, 1820 in the industrial city of Derby, England. After his preliminary education, he was employed by the railway company in 1836. During his unemployment, he wrote and taught himself, and based on this talent and the order of his uncle, Thomas Spencer, he started working in the "Economist" magazine. The death of his uncle Herbert Spencer in 1851 and the inheritance he left for him fulfilled his wish. He left his jobs and devoted himself to research in the field of common sciences of the time as a freelance writer and researcher. With his fascination and tact, he studied the contents and achievements of biological scientists such as Lamarck and Carpenter and applied his findings in the field of sociology. He never married[1] and after his death according to his will, his body was cremated. Herbert Spencer was a more or less withdrawn, introspective and almost individualistic and calm personality; Therefore, his colleagues in the London and Birmingham Railway Department did not pay much attention to him. He had a tendency to provoke the enmity of his superiors and whenever he felt that he was right, he would argue with them. Therefore, he was not a very likable person, but still he was highly respected. During the writing of social stagnation, Spencer's insomnia began and became so painful that he used opium to endure it. Over the years, his physical and mental illnesses worsened. So that he could only work a few hours a day. He suffered from nervous disorders for the rest of his life. Shortly after the publication of 'Principles of Psychology', Spencer developed an unknown neurological disease. There were times when he would walk around the city aimlessly for hours, and times when he could not read or write at all. He often withdrew from social gatherings, and towards the end of his life, even the thought of public speaking became excruciating for him. Not only was Spencer celibate for the rest of his life, he probably never had sex with a woman. At the beginning, he studied mathematics, chemistry, physics and anatomy in a scattered manner and then turned to natural sciences. After reading Darwin's book, he became firmer in his innovative view of the transformation and evolution of organisms, although before reading Darwin's works, he also benefited from the views of the naturalist Lamarck. His scientific philosophy, whose view was to clarify the phenomena of life, mind and society within the framework of the term matter, movement and force, was published in an eighteen-volume book. The foundation of his philosophy in clarifying the entire universe as a progressive movement from one stage to a more

complete stage was based on the "laws of evolution". Spencer's main interest is the study of transformation in social structures. According to Spencer, evolution moves from an indeterminate, incoherent and single-handed state to a coherent, heterogeneous and multi-handed state. The greater the differentiation, the greater the coherence and the stronger the dependence. From the beginning of his life, he was interested in discussing political, religious, and philosophical issues, and through studying and researching natural sciences, he achieved innovative and progressive theories. In this purpose, he suffered and the weakness of old age did not prevent his work. When he devoted himself to this work, Darwin's famous book had not yet been written, and when this book was published, Spencer became firmer in his philosophy and belief and used Darwin's research. Like Saint Simon, August Comte and Karl Marx, Spencer tried to interpret society and change it. In 1860, he started the masterpiece of his life called "Evolution". Spencer believed that the formation of bodies takes place due to the efforts of the constituent parts within themselves. The origin of such thinking that: evolution takes place independently and outside of divine providence or other power, was a revolutionary hypothesis in its era. In addition to biology, Spencer turned to the realm of sociology and then "ethics", which were probably considered at that time as successive degrees in the order of phenomena. Spencer succeeded in enriching general philosophy by presenting the principles derived from the hypothesis of evolution. He believed that: the galaxy moves as a huge group and is continuously completed in the direction of acquiring characteristics and separating and adjusting the elements, and in this way, it deals with more harmony between the constituent elements. In his Biological Treatises (1864–67), Spencer drew on Charles Darwin and Alfred Russel Walsh's views on the division of labor between organisms. Spencer moved to London in 1848 and worked as an editor in the Economist. With the death of his uncle (Thomas Spencer) in 1853, he inherited a huge fortune. As a result of acquiring this wealth, Spencer left his job at the Economist and continued to live as an independent scientist, without a permanent job or connection to the university.

thought

Spencer believes in the analogy of society with a biological organism based on the analogy of society with the organ of a living organism. He accepted the role of environmental variables in social organization and believed that supraorganic (community) and organism (organism) are similar to each other in six aspects:

Society and people grow.

As it grows, so do the complexities.

Progress in structure brings with it the decomposition of function.

The components of the whole are interdependent.

Every organism is a community.

Some parts die and others survive (not all members of society die at the same time).

However, Spencer felt that there were differences between the organism and society:

The difference in the degree of connection: in the organism, there is a close connection and a strong and objective connection between the members, while the society consists of separate and free individuals (individuals, if they wish, can join or leave the society).

The difference in the means of communication: in the organism, the communication between the members takes place through the movement of molecular particles, and in the society, through language.

Difference in consciousness: In an organism, the members exist to serve the whole, while in society, the whole exists to serve the individuals.

Spencer believes that all the forces of a living being can be divided into two parts:

The force of "preservation of essence"

The power of origin and creation or Manasaz

The theory of survival of the fittest

Spencer first used the term survival of the fittest in his book Principles of Biology in 1864. Spencer's most important contribution to the development of social thinking should be considered the proposal of this concept. Many mistakenly attribute the concept of survival of the fittest to Darwin; While Spencer proposed this concept about ten years before the publication of Darwin's thoughts on natural selection. Darwin later said that he essentially preferred Spencer's term survival of the fittest to his own term natural selection. Careniro later explained, the reason for this possible Darwinian preference was that in the idea of natural selection, it is inferred

that an intelligent agent (here nature) makes the selection in favor of humans. Whereas, based on Spencer's term of survival of the fittest, nature eliminates the "unfit" species rather than selecting. Spencer's theory of survival of the fittest is more understandable than Darwin's natural selection. Darwin was only interested in the process of changing biological species, while Spencer, in addition, dealt with social processes and the final result (survival of the fittest).

According to Spencer, the evolution of biological species and social species is basically related to the survival of the fittest. Based on this, the evolutionary processes purify the unsuitable species and the final result of this purification will be the formation of a more complete society. Spencer considered this result to be caused by natural processes and was a proponent of free economy or policy of non-intervention. The key to this process is "adaptation"; And in this thinking, people should change with changes in society (and environment). This fundamental idea, according to which there should be no intervention in the adjustment process, suggests that "incompetents" (the poor, the weak, the ignorant, or the sick) are "screened out." Spencer considered the natural process of the struggle for survival to be a kind of biological purification process. He says in the book *Social Statics*:

Apparently, it is difficult to leave widows and orphans in the struggle of life and death. However, if we consider this issue not in isolation, but in a way related to the interests of all mankind, we see that these terrible tragedies are full of benefits. ; Among other things, children of sick people die faster and abnormal and weak people are isolated as victims of epidemics.

Spencer was very hard-hearted about the poor and against the government helping them. In this regard, he wrote:

The law for the protection of the poor, which by suspending the adaptation process, will cause the expansion of the scope of poverty in the future, can have such a consequence today. Much of the money that is spent each year on helping the poor could be spent on supporting workers who work in productive sectors, such as draining land, building industrial machinery, and so on. In this way, warehouses will be quickly filled with manufactured goods and subsequently the shortage of goods will be eliminated. Spencer was against any kind of government intervention in private activities, and in his opinion, competition leads to the destruction of individuals who are biologically and socially incompetent. Spencer's individualistic

view and his belief in a free economy was warmly welcomed by American capitalists, as it provided them with an acceptable justification to attribute their privileged position to their superior virtues.

Economic Spencerism

The influence of Aslah Spencer's view on the survival of the fittest and the strongest species on the contemporary Iranian researcher Enayatollah Morshedi (in English: Enayatollah Morshedi) has been to the extent that this researcher has an organic view of the future ecosystem and the generalization of Spencer's view to the business ecosystem. And economic organizations have put forward a claim and a theory under the title of economic spencerism: the survival of the most compatible company and the choice of the future in his book entitled *Businesses of the Future World*. In short, according to the theory of economic spencerism, which was proposed by Inayat Elah Morshidi in his book, in the future economic ecosystem and its changes and the micro and macro business environments, Asalh organization, which is the most compatible company with changes and trends, will be victorious and stable. . In Morshidi's theory of economic spencerism, the most flexible organization or company means the most flexible organization against changes with the most learning organizational culture, which has the least resistance against innovative and technological changes and developments. The future world reveals itself. With an organic look at the concepts of the future and organization, Morshidi has extended and generalized Spencer's view of survival to the ecosystem of economic organizations and calls it Economic Spencerism. In 1861, he published the book *Intellectual, Moral and Physical Education*. In this treatise, he orders that the school curriculum, which has been common since the Renaissance movement, be completely changed and freed from the constraints of Greek and Roman language and literature. Instead of Greek and Latin, natural sciences should be taught and arrangements should be made so that all the people and the masses of the people benefit from education. Spencer was a serious, logical man and completely away from poetic illusions. He lacked taste, passion, love and the beauties of life, and he did not marry until the end of his life, and he did not pay attention to wealth. He lived for 83 years and finally died on December 8, 1903 in Brighton.

survival of the fittest

The term survival of the fittest was first used by Herbert Spencer in the book *Principles of Biology* in 1864. Spencer's most important contribution to the development of social thinking should be considered the proposal of this concept. Many mistakenly attribute the concept of survival of the fittest to Darwin; While Spencer proposed this concept about ten years before the publication of Darwin's thoughts on natural selection. Darwin later said that he essentially preferred Spencer's term survival of the fittest to his own term natural selection. Careniro explained later, the reason for this possible preference of Darwin was that in the idea of natural selection, an intelligent agent (nature) makes the selection in favor of humans. In contrast, according to Spencer's term survival of the fittest, nature eliminates "unfit" forms of species rather than selecting them. Spencer's theory of survival of the fittest is more understandable than Darwin's natural selection. Darwin was only concerned with the process of biological species change, while Spencer, in addition, dealt with social processes and the final result (survival of the fittest). According to Spencer, the evolution of biological species and social species is basically related to the survival of the fittest. Based on this, the evolutionary processes purify the unsuitable species and the final result of this purification will be the formation of a more complete society. Spencer considered this result to be caused by natural processes and was a proponent of free economy or policy of non-intervention. The key to this process is "adaptation"; And in this thinking, people should change with changes in society (and environment). This fundamental idea, according to which there should be no intervention in the adjustment process, suggests that "incompetents" (the poor, the weak, the ignorant, or the sick) are "screened out." Spencer considered the natural process of struggle for survival as a kind of biological purification process. He says in his book *Social Stability*: Apparently, it is difficult to leave widows and orphans in the struggle with life and death, however, if we consider this issue not separately, but in a way related to the interests of the whole humanity, we can see that these terrible disasters are full of benefits; Among other things, children of sick people die faster and abnormal and weak people are isolated as victims of epidemics. Spencer was very hesitant about the poor and against government assistance to them. In this regard, he wrote:

The law to support the poor, which by suspending the adaptation process, will cause the expansion of the scope of poverty in the future, can have such a consequence today. A large part of the money that is spent each year on helping the poor goes to

support workers who are employed in the productive sectors, such as draining land, building industrial machinery, etc. In this way, warehouses will be quickly filled with manufactured goods and subsequently the shortage of goods will be eliminated. Spencer was against any government intervention in private activities, and in his opinion, competition causes the destruction of individuals who are not biologically and socially competent. Spencer's individualistic view and his belief in a free economy were warmly welcomed by American capitalists, as Barry provided them with a pleasing justification for attributing their privileged position to their superior virtues.

Criticisms

James Kennedy, criticizing Spencer's theory of survival of reform, says:

Spencer claimed that competent people thrive in situations where incompetent people are unable to thrive. Meanwhile, Spencer's own life was settled with the inheritance that came to him from his uncle; Therefore, his "qualification" for survival should be considered due to his family wealth.

Natural selection, natural selection or natural selection is a process that in successive generations causes the spread of those hereditary traits that increase the probability of survival and reproduction of an organism in a population. In other words, natural selection is a process during which people adapted to the environment have more chances to survive and reproduce and can pass their genes to the next generation. On the other hand, individuals incompatible with the environment are removed from the species and cannot pass on their genes. During this process, genes adapted to the environment remain in the species.

This process is one of the key mechanisms of evolution. Within a population of living things, genetic diversity causes that in the current habitat of that population, some members of the group are more likely to survive and reproduce than others. As an example, we can name the pepper moth, which is found in the UK, and both light and dark colors can be seen in nature. During the Industrial Revolution, many of the trees on which the willows rested were blackened by soot. Dark-colored willows gained more points for survival and reproduction due to being hidden from predators, and after only a few generations, the dark-colored group formed the majority of willows.

Factors that are effective on successful reproduction are also of great importance. Darwin proposed this in his ideas as sexual selection.

Although natural selection acts on the appearance traits (phenotype) of an organism, in fact, the gene, which is the heritable part and the basis of all such appearance traits (phenotype) of an organism, by increasing its prevalence in the population, causes an increase in the prevalence of such positively selected traits. Over time, this process can cause the organism to adapt to a special habitat and may eventually lead to the emergence of new species. Although natural selection is not the only process that causes evolution within a population of organisms, it should be considered one of the most important effective processes.

Natural selection is one of the basic foundations of modern biology. This word was introduced by Charles Darwin in his famous book "Principle of Species" or "Origin of Species" in 1859. In that book, Darwin explains this phenomenon by comparing artificial selection with natural selection. Artificial selection is a process in which plants and animals are selected for breeding by breeders based on their desirable traits from the point of view of humans (plant breeding, livestock breeding and microbial breeding). Natural selection was proposed when there was still no valid theory to explain heredity. Although Gregor Mendel, the father of genetics, was the same age as Darwin, his science and name remained unknown until the beginning of the 20th century, and no information about modern genetics was published during Darwin's time. Today, the link between Darwinian evolution and the findings of classical genetics and molecular genetics is called the modern synthesis of evolution. Natural selection is still the main explanation of adaptive evolution.

Basic principles

Members of a population of organisms are naturally different. Many of these differences do not have a direct effect on the organism's ability to survive, while some differences can have a positive effect on the organism's ability to survive. A rabbit that runs faster is more likely to be successful in escaping the clutches of predators. Algae that can better use the energy of sunlight grows faster. People who have a better chance to survive will have a better chance to reproduce. If such traits that increase the power of these people in breeding are hereditary and transferable from parent to child, then the population ratio of fast rabbits or efficient algae in the

next generation will increase slightly. Even if this reproductive advantage is very small, over many generations, due to exponential growth, most individuals in a population will exhibit beneficial heritable traits. In this way, the natural habitat and living environment of an organism "selects" the trait that is beneficial for reproduction and slowly causes the change and evolution of life. Darwin named and explained this phenomenon for the first time.

Philosophical definition

If x has more fitness than Y in environment E , then there is a possibility that x has more descendants than Y in environment E . Here x and Y can be individual genes, genotypes, organisms, groups, species, or possibly any other biological entity.

fit

In the discussion of natural selection, the concept of fitness [note 2] is of special importance. As mentioned in the famous phrase "survival of the fittest", people who are more prepared and fit will have a higher potential ability to continue living. However, as with the definition of natural selection, fitness can make a wide difference of opinion, so much so that Richard Dawkins has avoided using the term altogether in his recent books. (In his book *The Expanded Phenotype*, he devoted a chapter to discussing the cases in which the term has been used to describe those cases). In the modern theory of evolution, fitness is not defined based on the length of life of an organism, but is measured by the success of that organism in reproduction. If an organism lives for half the life of other members of its species, but at the same time produces twice as many children that are able to reach adulthood, its genes will become more common in the adult population of the next generation. Although natural selection acts on individuals, the role of chance causes fitness to have an average effect on individuals in the population. The fitness of a genotype is related to the average effect that genotype has on all people who have that genotype. A genotype with very low fitness causes people with that trait to have fewer children or no children at all. An example is genetic disorders in humans such as cystic fibrosis.

Since the fitness of a trait is an average effect, it is possible that a beneficial mutation in an individual is lost if that organism does not reach adulthood for any other reason. Fit is also highly dependent on living environment. Sickle cell anemia may

be considered a disadvantage in normal human population, but because the sickle trait protects a person from malaria to some extent, in human populations with high malaria infection, this trait is considered an advantage.

Examples of natural selection

Resistance of microorganisms to antibiotics is a well-known example of natural selection. Since the discovery of penicillin by Alexander Fleming in 1928, antibiotics have been widely used to treat bacterial diseases. Naturally, there are countless numbers of bacteria in a population of bacteria. In addition, the diversity of genetic material in bacteria (mostly due to mutation) is very impressive. Many bacteria are quickly killed when exposed to antibiotics. However, some of them are slightly more resistant to antibiotics due to mutation and will survive if only exposed to antibiotics for a short time. This selective removal of non-resistant bacteria from the population is similar to natural selection. The remaining bacteria will multiply and produce the next generation. Due to the elimination of incompatible and non-resistant bacteria in the previous generation, the current population will have a greater number of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. Simultaneously, new mutations will occur in the population and increase the genetic diversity among individuals in the group. Spontaneous mutations are extremely rare, and beneficial spontaneous mutations are even rarer. However, due to the very high number of bacteria in a population, few beneficial mutations may occur. If these new mutations make the bacteria resistant to the antibiotic, the bacteria will have a better chance of surviving if they are re-exposed to the antibiotic. When this process occurs for a long time and bacteria are continuously exposed to antibiotics, a population of antibiotic-resistant bacteria will emerge. This population will be completely compatible with its evolutionary process. It should be noted that the mentioned process will not increase the adaptation of bacteria in the environment without antibiotics.

The widespread use of antibiotics has increased the drug resistance of microbes to antibiotics. This is an example of an evolutionary arms race. In this race, bacteria increase their resistance to antibiotics, and on the other hand, medical scientists are trying to find newer antibiotics that can kill these microbes. A similar situation can be seen in the resistance developed in plants and insects to herbicides and insecticides. It should not be forgotten that these arms races are not necessarily induced by humans.

Evolution through natural selection

In order for natural selection to cause evolution, new traits and new species, it is necessary to have heritable genetic diversity that causes the diversity of people's adaptations. Genetic diversity is the result of mutation, recombination (breaking a nucleic acid and rejoining it to another nucleic acid molecule, such as occurs in meiosis) and karyotypic changes (changes in the number, shape, size, and internal arrangement of chromosomes). Each of these changes can cause a very profitable or very valuable effect, but the occurrence of a significant effect is a very rare event. In the past, most of the changes made in the genetic material were considered neutral or close to neutral, and the reason for this was the occurrence of these changes in the non-key part of DNA (non-coding part of DNA) which leads to the replacement of the same name. However, in recent researches The deleterious effect of many mutations that occur in the non-core part of DNA has been suggested. According to the definition of fitness, individuals who are more compatible have a higher probability of reproduction and are more likely to die prematurely or fail to reproduce than incompatible individuals. As a result, the alleles that cause higher fitness on average will be more abundant in the next generation. On the other hand, the alleles that cause a decrease in fitness will become rarer in the next generations. If selective pressures do not cause significant change over successive generations, beneficial alleles will slowly become more abundant and eventually dominate. In this situation, incompatible alleles will gradually disappear. Spontaneous mutations and recombinations occur in each generation, which will create a new range of phenotypes. This process will cause beneficial alleles to multiply over many generations. Created attributes will not be immutable. Traits that are considered beneficial in one environment may not be so beneficial due to changing environmental conditions. In new conditions, such a trait will no longer be selected by natural selection and will slowly undergo change and destruction or will show itself as a vestigial symbol of a trait. In many cases, the vestigial structure retains its function in a very limited way or it will find a new function during a phenomenon called pre-adaptation (pre-adaptation is a phenomenon in which an organism uses the previous anatomical structure received from its ancestors for a new purpose An example of this is the use of feathers by dinosaurs, which were originally developed as thermal insulation. The same situation can be seen in the transformation of sweat glands into mammary glands. A famous example is the vestigial structure of the eye

in the blind mouse, which is probably used to understand the changes in day length during the seasons.

Emergence of new species (speciation)

The emergence of new species requires selective mating, because this process reduces gene flow (gene flow is the transfer of gene alleles from one population to another, which is also called gene migration). Selective mating, for example, can occur as a result of a change in the physical environment (for example, as a result of the physical separation of a group following the creation of an external barrier) or as a result of sexual selection. Over time, the resulting subspecies may diverge so much that they form new species. These differences can be caused by the difference in selection pressures on different subgroups, the occurrence of new mutations in subgroups, or the founder effect (reduction of genetic diversity due to the creation of a new population from a very small number of individuals). The genetic changes in the subgroups increase the heterogeneity between the genetic material of the two subgroups, and for this reason, the gene flow between the groups decreases. When the known mutations that characterize each subtype reach a stable state, gene flow will practically stop. It should be kept in mind that even a small number of mutations can lead to the creation of new species and for such a change, even the occurrence of two mutations can be enough. Imagine that a mutation that has a positive or neutral effect on members of one group occurs, and another positive or neutral mutation occurs within other members of the group. Now imagine that these mutations, which are beneficial or ineffective by themselves, can be harmful or lethal when present together in an organism. This problem will be an obstacle for breeding between the two groups. If the mentioned genes are stable in these two groups, two population groups that are reproductively separate will be formed. Based on the biological definition of species, these two groups will form two separate species.

Historical developments

Pre-Darwinian theories

Several ancient philosophers believed that nature creates a wide variety of organisms randomly, and only those organisms that are able to reproduce successfully will survive. Examples of these philosophers include Empedocles and

his successor Lucretius. After some time, Aristotle improved these theories. After some time, Jahiz explained the struggle for survival. He mentioned that the surrounding factors trigger the creation of traits in animals that are the guardians of their lives. Abu Rihan Boruni explained the artificial selection and reminded that nature also works with a similar process. Nasir al-Din Tusi and Ibn Khaldun also had similar theories. These old theories were revisited in the 18th century by Pierre-Louis Maupertouseau, then others, including Erasmus Darwin (Charles Darwin's grandfather).

Synthesis of modern evolution

Natural selection is strongly dependent on the concept of heredity, while natural selection was proposed for the first time, long before the basic principles of genetics were understood. Although the Austrian monk Gregor Mendel, considered the father of modern genetics, was a contemporary of Darwin, his work remained largely unknown until the early 20th century. Natural selection was accepted by most scientists only after combining Darwin's theory of evolution with a sophisticated statistical understanding of Mendel's laws of inheritance. Ronald Fisher's work (he completed the mathematical language needed for the genetic hypothesis of natural selection) JBS Haldane (he applied and explained the concept of "cost" in natural selection) Wright's question (he clarified the concept of selection and activity adaptation Teodosius Dobzhansky (he introduced mutation as the creator of genetic variation, the factor creating the raw material needed for natural selection) William Donald Hamilton (he explained the concept of ethnic selection) Ernest Meyer (he explained the important role of reproductive separation in the production of species Newly proposed) and many other scientists, led to the creation of the modern evolutionary synthesis. This synthesis still emphasizes the key role of natural selection in the theory of evolution.

Genetic explanation of evolution

Today, with the advancement of genetic science and biotechnology, the ability to compare the DNA of people and living things through molecular markers has been provided. This capability is used to identify the kinship of living beings with each other, as well as in criminology and to distinguish between parents and children in judicial and legal issues; DNA testing has shown that the difference between human and chimpanzee DNA is about one percent, and this is a confirmation of evolution.

mechanism

Hereditary variation, differential reproduction

There is a possibility of natural variation occurring among the individuals of any population. Some differences may improve an individual's chances of surviving and reproducing, so that lifetime fertility increases, meaning more children are born.

fitness or viability

The concept of fitness or biological ability is fundamental to natural selection. In general, people who are more "fit" have a better potential for survival, as in the popular phrase "survival of the fittest," but the precise meaning of this term is much more nuanced. The modern evolutionary theory explains fitness or biological ability according to not the length of time an organism lives, but according to its success rate in reproduction.

competition

In biology, competition is an interaction between organisms in which the fitness of one is reduced by the presence of another. The reason for this could be that both are limited to the same resource such as food, water, habitat.

classification

Natural selection can act on any phenotypic heritable trait, and selection pressure can be induced by any aspect of the environment, including sexual selection and competition with members of one or other species. However, this does not mean that natural selection is always directional and causes adaptive evolution. Natural selection usually maintains conditions by eliminating those most incompatible with the status quo.

By influencing the character

Natural selection has various effects on traits. Stable selection works in the direction of keeping the desired state constant, and in the simplest case, all deviations from the desired state are considered undesirable selection.

By influencing genetic diversity

On the other hand, selection can be divided according to its effect on genetic variation. Purification, or negative selection, acts to eliminate genetic changes from a population (as opposed to re-mutation, which introduces new changes).[7]

by life cycle stage

Another option for classifying selection is at what stage of the life cycle it occurs. Some biologists have identified only two examples, one of which is selection based on viability (survival). This selection means that the probability of survival of an organism will increase according to its viability, fertility (life span and reproduction), which will increase reproduction and survival.

with the unit of choice

Selection can also be classified by the amount or unit of selection. Individual choice acts on a single person and adaptations are in line with the individual's benefit, and this result can be achieved through individual choice.

with a resource over which there is competition

Finally, selection can be made by a resource that there is competition to obtain. Sexual selection occurs as a result of competition to find a mate. Sexual selection is often done by fertility selection and sometimes by viability selection. Ecological selection is also an example of natural selection, which has a different meaning than sexual selection. such as clan selection, competition and infanticide.

Social Stability, or Certain Necessary Conditions for Their Happiness and Development, is a book written in 1851 by Herbert Spencer (27 April 1820 – 8 December 1903), a philosopher, biologist, anthropologist, sociologist and prominent English classical liberal political theorist of the Victorian era, and written by John Chapman. Published in London.

In this book, he uses the term "organism" to apply his Lamarckian ideas. For example, for the evolution of society, he says: it is clear that every being whose structure is supposed to be adapted to the new conditions of existence must be subjected to those conditions, or if we express this statement specifically, it is clear that man can only be maintained in the social situation. adapt to the social situation.

Obviously, the result is that since man is and is deficient in those sentiments which, by dictating just conduct, prevent the perpetual conflict of individuals and their consequent separation, some artificial agency is required by which to unite them. be preserved Only through the adaptation process can one create a personality that creates social balance by itself.

It is often believed that in this same book and before the publication of the book "Principles of Biology" (1864), Spencer coined the phrase "survival of the fittest". which he later used in economics and biology. This can be described as a key tenet of so-called social Darwinism, although Spencer and his book did not advocate it.

"Social Stability" is Spencer's first important book in the field of political philosophy. It attempts to base a limited government on a careful development of the doctrine of natural rights. He begins by defending his "first principle": "Each man may claim such perfect liberty as to the exercise of his faculties, which is consistent with the same liberty enjoyed by every other man." According to Spencer, government is not a "necessary" institution and will "degenerate" when the voluntary organization of the market replaces the coercive aspects of government. He also argued that the individual has the right to ignore the government.

Herbert Spencer's writing style and views

Although Herbert Spencer has left many works in various fields of social, political and cultural sciences, he is most famous for his theory of survival of the fittest. He believed in the ideology of liberal capitalism and the non-interference of the government in any social process. He believed that the government and society should prevent helping the weak, sick and helpless and allow these social groups to be eliminated during the process of biological purification. until finally an ideal society is formed.

Despite the similarity between Charles Darwin's theory of evolution and Spencer's theory of survival of the fittest, there is an important difference between these two theories. According to the theory of evolution, the acceptance of living organisms and their survival depends on their biological compatibility; On the other hand, Herbert Spencer believed that people in society adapt to the physical environment not through biological adaptation, but through culture. This author also believed that those who can quickly adapt to cultural changes in the environment are more likely

to achieve social success, enjoy it and can pass the benefits of this achievement to their children. After its publication, the theory of survival of the fittest was welcomed by some extreme conservatives; Especially among a part of the white American society that President Abraham Lincoln's efforts to abolish slavery were in conflict with their economic and social interests. Since then, this theory of Herbert Spencer had many critics, and after his death, the theory of survival of the fittest lost some of its credibility due to its hostile approach towards the deprived classes. Because critics believed that Spencer consciously ignores stratification and structured social inequalities in order not only to reduce the responsibility of the government and society towards the deprived class, but also to prevent any social support from this social group.

Herbert Spencer through the eyes of others

- Herbert Spencer is one of the most valuable people I have ever met. He is one of the most prominent scientists in history. (Charles Darwin)
- Herbert Spencer, the father of the theory of natural selection, was not actually a sociologist; Because instead of studying society, he was inspired by biological studies and proposed his theory based on that. (Emile Durkheim)

Facts about Herbert Spencer

- Herbert Spencer was a quiet, sullen, isolated and reclusive person and did not marry until the end of his life.
- Herbert Spencer's theories had many fans in America in the 20th century.
- Herbert Spencer never went to school and learned mathematics and experimental science privately and self-taught.
- The severity of Herbert Spencer's nervous disease was such that he resorted to using opium to reduce his pain.

Selected quotes of Herbert Spencer

- Intelligence in creatures, from the lowest to the highest, usually develops in a discriminating manner, and this is also true among human beings, from the slowest to the most intelligent. Understanding the differences and being able to correctly classify things or things of similar nature in one place, and things or things of

different nature in another place, is a basic condition for the development of mind functions. (Man versus the State book)

- Apparently, it is difficult to leave widows and orphans in the struggle of life and death. However, if we consider this issue not separately, but in a way related to the interests of the whole mankind, we see that these terrible disasters are full of benefits; Including that, children of sick people die faster and abnormal and weak people are isolated as victims of epidemic diseases. (book of social stability)

Herbert Spencer was born in Derby, England in 1820. His family had an individualistic view. His book "Social Statics" which related the ideas raised in the realm of decent government, and his second book was "Principles of Sociology" and then numerous articles of his main information from The way of talking with others was born and because he did not participate in the classroom, stereotyped thoughts did not take root in him, he believed in brain and intellectual health.

Spencer took the terms "sociology" and "philanthropy" or "social harmony" from Kent and considered himself indebted to Kent's teaching that "organizational principles are common among human and animal societies and the evolution of structures progressed from the general to the particular." He does. Darwin introduces Spencer in his evolutionary theory, but it is not correct to call Spencer a social Darwinist because Spencer's main doctrine was made before Darwin published a work on evolution.

He is one of the evolutionary sociologists who, inspired by Darwin's biology and theories, proposed the "organism theory" as the gradual progress of social life from simple forms to complex forms, from homogeneity to increasing heterogeneity. Biological speculations had a privileged place among Spencer's sociological arguments, and since he was a strong individualist, organic speculations caused him philosophical and sociological difficulties, the result of using Spencer's organic speculations was to It was understood that evolutionary growth in the structure and functions of each unit produces changes that cause an increase in volume and as a result more differentiation of its components.

Spencer defines evolution as: "a change from a relatively indeterminate, incoherent and homogeneous state to a relatively definite, coherent and diverse state" and this evolution includes both the first transformations of the world and the last

transformations that occur in the products of life. We find social explains and the evolution of human societies is nothing but a special case of the law that has universal application.

Spencer believed that social growth is done in two ways:

1- Sometimes separated from each other: it is obtained due to increase in population or by simple multiplication of units.

2- Sometimes they merge together: joining together units that were not connected before, that is, by uniting groups and again by uniting groups of groups.

Spencer sees the result of increase in volume as an increase in the complexity of structures as a result of more and more differentiation of functions and structures, which results in increasing interdependence and finally the integration of components, so the result of the process of growth is the process of integration.

According to Spencer, evolution is the integration and integration of matter, which is associated with terms and decomposition of movement, and matter that passes from the state of indeterminate and chaotic homogeneity to the state of definite and orderly multiplicity.

In the discussion of the evolution of society, sociologists generally believed in two types of evolution:

1- The evolution of a single line which has a longer history means that all human societies go through certain and unavoidable stages, and the transition from each stage to another stage is regular and must be passed through the stages in order. Undoubtedly, all human societies will pass this way.

2- The theory of multi-linear evolution: Some believe that societies can go through different paths, while another group says that societies have passed the path of modernity, but with ups and downs and sometimes even going back and forth, that is, sometimes societies are possible. Regressive garlic or go into degeneration.

Spencer did not believe in linear evolution: "A social organism, like an individual organism, accepts many transformations in order to reach a balance with its

environmental conditions, but after that, it can continue to live without accepting any further changes in its structure."

{Societies evolve in response to their social and natural environment}

To understand the origin and development of an organization, one must see what needs this organization had to fulfill in the beginning and later. Social institutions are not the result of intentional intentions and motivations of social actors, but originate from functional and structural requirements {conditions are decisive, not intentions}

From the general principles of Spencer's point of view, it can be mentioned that he believed:

"The properties of the constituent units of the society determine the properties of the society.

Two topics are mixed in Spencer's theories:

- 1- Evolutionary stages mentioned in biology
- 2- Changes and transformations of human society throughout history

And Spencer's work is important in his era in two ways:

- 1- Solving the problem of the relationship between philosophy and empirical sciences and defining philosophy as a unifying knowledge that curbs the dispersion and excessive specialization of sciences.
- 2- Presenting a practical theory about the phenomenon of development, especially social and historical development. Spencer refers to the word "society" as a group of people whose distribution of parts has special durability and consistency and their lives are fixed in a specific place.

In Spencer's opinion, society is a superior organ that is obtained from the combination of individual organs, and culture in today's sense is seen as a system of mutual relations of actions and thoughts in his writings.

He compares the society to a living organ that has organs and organs. In his opinion, the whole society has a certain function, in such a way that he compares the government to the head, the army and economic activities to other organs, and

human communities are like a He believes that the living organism is growing and evolving. He does not consider the development of society to depend on one factor, but believes that the path of evolution is determined by an unknown force and there is no single determining factor to explain the changes and transformations of society.

Spencer was of the opinion that change and development in society is based on unforeseen results and in sync with the expected results, and this has made complete planning impossible.

He draws parallels between the growth of organic collections and social collections:

- 1- Both of them start their growth from an undifferentiated state.
- 2- First, the components of a set are similar to each other, then they become differentiated and dissimilar.
- 3- Social and organic collections are interdependent.
- 4- Increasing differentiation is associated with increasing interdependence and integration of components.
- 5- Both movements are in the direction of growth and development.
- 6- Both have expansion in size, dimensions, complexity and structural increase.
- 7- The division of duties between the components of both is completely evident.

He distinguishes between social and biological organism, including:

- 1- The parts of the organism form a whole, but the parts of the society form a separate whole.
- 2- The units that make up the organism are stuck together, but the units of the society are free and scattered.
- 3- Coherence between the parts of an organism is necessary and essential, but the parts of a society do not form a whole.
- 4- The components of the social organism can influence each other through mediators such as language.

- 5- The exchange of messages in the organism is through physical stimulation, but in society, the exchange of messages is through language and emotion.
- 6- In the organism, awareness is concentrated in a small part, but in society, awareness is scattered throughout the whole complex.
- 7- There are physical nerves in the organism, but in the society, the welfare of the whole cannot be separate from the welfare of its component units.
- 8- The organs of the body are alive by means of nerves (center), but the society exists for its organs.[1]
- 9- The members of the organism are all involved in the same news, but the members of the society have relative independence.
- 10- There is complete lack of coordination between the components of the social organism.
- 11- Each component of a social system has its own perception and emotional sensitivities, which causes choice and differences in their actions.
- 12- The independence of opinion and sensory differences in human emotional perception, which unlike the components in the organism, can bring relatively significant changes in one's life.
- 13- Biological entities have specific, fixed and visible external forms, while society does not have such a form.
- 14- The units of a biological entity are physically related to each other, while the members of a society may be scattered in a wide area and not have direct contact with each other.
- 15- The parts of an organism remain in a fixed and stable state in terms of their position relative to each other, while the people of a society do not necessarily live in one place and are able to move from one point to another and reorganize their spatial relationships.
- 16- Self-awareness is only in one part of the biological existence (in the brain), while every person in the society is capable of having independent self-awareness.

Spencer was influenced by the opinions of evolutionists of his time such as Darwin, Lamarck, on the one hand, being influenced by the opinions of demographers such as Malthus, laid the foundation of good social philosophy. By putting forward the principle of "struggle for survival", Malthus considers the society as a battlefield where people are engaged in war and conflict in order to obtain the means of life. Spencer puts this principle together with Darwin's principle of "natural selection" as the basis of his social theories and proposes the principle of "survival of the fittest" or "survival of the fittest".

Spencer's belief in survival of the fittest was that as the population increases, it needs more intelligence to survive, so the least intelligent groups and individuals will die, and as a result, the general level of intelligence will be gradually and inevitably high, so only those who have superior intelligence will survive. They can survive the battle for survival. His famous book "Synthetic Philosophy" has planned the construction of an ideal society based on the principle of free competition and the principle of compatibility and natural selection. He proposed to dissolve all the institutions that prevent the flow of forced and rational natural laws.

Societies, like other parts of existence, are subject to natural laws, and the principle of natural selection is dominant and suitable for the continuation of life, therefore, any interference in internal affairs and any type of activity whose purpose is to support the weak and poor is rejected due to the disruption of natural laws. and it not only leads to deviation and chaos, but also causes the degeneration and destruction of societies. Man has no role in Spencer's sociological system except as a functional agent. Spencer emphasizes that the principle of natural selection alone is able to guide societies in the path of improvement and development. He prohibits the government from interfering in the following matters:

- 1- Establishing commercial regulations
- 2- Interfering in the affairs of religious institutions
- 3- Establishing charitable institutions to help the poor and weak
- 4- Interfering in matters related to education and training
- 5- Interfering in health and treatment affairs

Spencer believed that the application of severe restrictions and direct actions in the society will not result in the desired improvement and reform, therefore, he considers the role of individuals and reformer movements to be very insignificant in changing the direction of society's development. According to Spencer, society is

an entity with its own special structure and with organs and members that are responsible for each specific function, and it is the maintenance of these functions that makes the system and the overall structure of society possible in the direction of growth and expansion, because the growth and expansion of societies The result is more structure and separation of functions between organs.

Complexity in roles and increasing functional separation from Spencer's meeting is one of the most important criteria for the progress of societies.

Spencer considers the basic processes of growth, separation, integration and adaptive improvement to a certain extent dependent on the following factors:

- 1- External factors such as access to natural resources
- 2- Internal factors such as the nature of internal units
- 3- He knew concrete factors such as the existence of other societies with internal values and beliefs.

Spencer describes the development stages of societies according to TE Vari Tekamuli himself states as follows: 1- Simple society 2- Composite society 3- Double composite society 4- Three-faceted or multi-faceted or three-fold composite society.

A: Simple societies:

- 1- Your lack of leadership
- 2- People's way of life is simple.
- 3- There is very little conflict and if there is a conflict of interest, it will be controlled automatically.
- 4- No need for a leader
- 5- A secretive society without a leader
- 6- Cooperation with each other in work
- 7- More pastoral way of living
- 8- Non-specialization of work such as Eskimos and Guinean tribes

B: Composite society

- 1- Occasional or situational leadership
- 2- The stratification of society in the form of ruling and condemned strata
- 3- The way of living based on agriculture
- 4- Small and simple industrial structures were seen like the Teutonic people - Greeks in the period of Homer
- 5- Division of work has been done in an elementary way

C: Double or dual composite society

- 1- The growth of society
- 2- Leadership becomes more necessary in different situations.
- 3- Leadership is semi-permanent or unstable and there is no special organization to maintain the leader.
- 4- They are completely settled.
- 5- The political structure is bigger than the composite society.
- 6- Religious hierarchy is seen in it.
- 7- A more complicated division of labor is seen.. such as France in the 13th century and England in the 11th century
- 8- Customs have become immutable laws.
- 9- Cities have been created.

D: Three-faceted composite society

- 1- The perfection of societies is seen.
- 2- Sustainable leadership
- 3- Completion of dispersions in terms of division of work
- 4- Pure connection

5- The transformation of homogeneity into heterogeneity like the nations of great civilization such as modern Britain, Germany and Russia

6- Increasing the need for control

7- Establishing a stable government

8- Population dispersion

9- Division of intense and specialized work

Spencer has another division of society and it is in terms of the relationship of each society with its neighbor. which divides the societies into two groups, warrior and hardworking or industrial, the classification and separation of warrior and industrial societies is based on social organization and differences in social organization.

Warrior society:

1- Conflict relations between it and neighboring societies should be based on the originality of outgroup conflict

2- The government is omnipotent.

3- The number of public social organizations and institutions is more than private organizations and institutions.

4- The principle of concentration is strictly followed.

5- There is a forced cooperation (such as the subordination of the external organs of the body to the central nervous system)

6- Blind information, pure obedience to leadership power, having national bias and lack of vertical social mobility.

7- Societies are subject to the will of the government and forceful supervisions rule the society.

8- Division of society into military ranks

9- The external regulating device dominates the internal holder.

Industrious or industrial society

- 1- Internal regulatory systems are relatively weak and scattered.
- 2- The special industry of these societies is voluntary cooperation and individual self-restraint
- 3- The main regulatory body of the decentralized society and the power of the individual is obtained from different classes of the society.
- 4- Outgroup conflict is controlled by peaceful behavior.
- 5- The relationship of people with each other and with the government is of voluntary cooperation.
- 6- The principle of individual freedom is observed and freedom of opinion and religion
- 7- The role of the government is established as an observer and protector of people's social and economic rights, and its purpose is to protect the rights of individuals.
- 8- No class gap.
- 9- Existence of private and charitable organizations
- 10- Election of the government by the people

Spencer affirms the social foundation of capitalist societies, in addition, there is no time lag or evolutionary order between these two societies, that is, every industrial society was not necessarily a warrior before, or every warrior society does not become an industrial society.

He classified the members of the society in terms of social traits as:

- 1- The king: a practical example of the power of nature, which is summed up in the power of the king.
- 2- The king's advisers who have the duty of intellectual advice.
- 3- The majority of people who have the duty of obeying the king and performing duties.

Spencer defines three types of government:

1- Monarchy: Although it is bad, it is the most practical form of government, because if force rules the society, all members act on its basis, so a king is necessary to reduce the difference in procedure (it is the best type of government).

2- Oligarchy or illumination

3- Democracy and democrats: because it requires consciousness and awareness to a certain extent and people's consciousness and awareness have not yet developed, so democracy cannot be suitable for current societies.

He considers the mental, psychological, and behavioral characteristics of the people of each society under the influence of the influence of the government and the way it deals with the outgroup conflict and practically the social structure of each of these two types of society, which ultimately results in two types of social relations. Give: 1- Relationships based on coercion and imposition 2- Relationships based on voluntary cooperation and based on social contracts

Spencer accepted the negative performance of some elements in the society, but he believed that the society as a whole exists in a state of functional interaction. The word balance in Spencer's words does not refer to a static state, but refers to a dynamic process.

Spencer divides the functional groups of society into 3 devices:

1- A holding or internal device that is related to the production of goods.

2- The regulatory or external body that is responsible for establishing political order and organizing the military machine of the society.

3- Distributing device that connects the regulating and maintaining device together, like communication channels in society.

Spencer considers the fear of death to be the reason for the emergence of religions. Man imagines God and gods or forces to defend and persevere against his fear in order to reduce this fear by holding on to them.

Fear of the living also causes the establishment of the government because the interests of people are threatened and attacked by each other. And people are not able to deal with it, they resort to establishing social contracts and every law and contract needs an executive guarantee, so the duty of the government is to control

and properly implement the laws, so one of the functions of the government can be to reduce intra-group conflict and increase the spirit of cooperation in society. knew

The only power that Spencer has given to the government is to protect the rights of individuals and protect against foreign enemies. The rest of the affairs should be left to the free initiative of the people of the society so that they can arrange their lives through contracts and mutual agreements.

Spencer considers the cause of the emergence of the political system to be the interdependence of disparate elements in complex societies and the resulting fragility, which requires a regulatory system to monitor the actions of the elements of society and ensure harmony between them. Having a regulatory system is at the beginning of the process of social evolution, the regulatory centers were for communication with the external environment, such as enemies, animals, and hunting, but with the progress of the evolution of these centers, they take over the function of regulating internal affairs and social supervision.

Criteria for classifying societies according to Spencer:

- 1- Strictness and scope of action of the regulatory power of internal affairs
- 2- It is the degree of evolutionary complexity of societies.

In urban sociology, Spencer Shiva examines the relationship between people and their leader and analyzes the ecology of society.

It divides the societies into types: 1- desert or nomadic 2- semi-sedentary 3- sedentary.

And in another division, he divides societies into hunter-gatherer, 2- sedentary, 3- tribal.

1- desert dweller:

- Logic with simple society (in political sociology)
- Some characteristics of mixed societies
- He has experienced leadership from time to time
- Adaptation to tribal society

2- Sit half together:

- Animal husbandry and home industries
- Lack of permanent stability in a region
- Compliance with the dual composite society (in political sociology)
- Adapting to the hunter-gatherer society where the allocation of functions is primary (farmer and warrior)

3- Community sit together:

- Permanent stability in one place
- Government in fixed government
- The stage of regional agriculture
- Compliance with the three-faceted composite stage (in political sociology)
- Distinguishing the role of farmer and warrior

The concepts derived from Spencer's theory is a concept of absolute and pure determinism that governs the natural world, all the laws that exist in nature are also true in human society, and the movement is scattered among matter and causes them to change their shape. Humans have no role, this issue brings to mind Smith's "invisible hand" theory. Smith believed that the market has a mechanism as "invisible government" that maintains its entire state in a natural state. Spencer also said that action and Reciprocal reactions of nature governs the world by itself and man cannot interfere in it. Interfering in natural affairs is disbelief and polytheism. Effort is the essence of natural history and tradition that man must strive, but the effort of each individual is the health and strength of life and Success does not confirm his life.

The difference between the Islamic concept and Spencer's concept

Our idea of God is a being with absolute intelligence and absolute knowledge

Spencer's nature has absolute power without will and consciousness

Spencer's nature is blind.

He considers memory and intelligence to be reflections of matter.

Will is a reflection of nature.

The will in the evolutionary direction is normal behavior if it is contrary to the evolutionary process, it is a violation of nature. As a result of Spencer's determinism, he founded a school called "Unbounded Sociology" which sought an unbounded economic model. Smith appeared in this way, he was against all the social programs of the governments that were in favor of eliminating poverty and working towards the development of health and welfare.

Spencer's main problem is that in pursuit of replacing and generalizing natural laws to social affairs, and because he considers nature to be omnipotent and the only guide, he is drawn to the philosophy of determinism.

Spencer was subject to the metaphysical theory of the single model. This theory has poems that the reality is the gradual product of small but continuous changes that happen over long periods. This theory of the single model gives Spencer's work an extremely positive orientation. Nevertheless, towards the end of his life, Spencer seems to have put the continuous forward change in the corner and accepted the concept of "rhythmic" change, that is, although the change is mostly forward, there may be periods of in between. There should be continuous periods of development.

Spencer believed that definite conclusions can be drawn where the data are few and complete, and where the data are numerous and incomplete, the conclusion will be vague and uncertain. Mathematics for the first case and sociology for the second case. is

In his study, Spencer divided the sciences into two main groups:

- 1- Exact sciences such as physics, chemistry and astronomy
- 2- Inexact sciences such as sociology, psychology, geology and biology

The reason for considering Spencer to be functionalist (cohesive and resistant functionalist) to the government :

- 1- It considers all the components of existence as small elements that interact with each other to maintain the system and move towards the overall goals of that system.

2- To understand any social issue, we must know the function of social construction.

Finally, we pay attention to the difference between Kent and Spencer:

1- Kent unilinear evolution, but Spencer multilinear evolution

2- Kent was an anti-individualist and considered the individual as an unquestionable subordinate of the society, but Spencer considered the individualist and the society to advance the goals of individuals.

3- In Spencer's opinion, the continuity of people is to achieve profit.

4- According to Spencer, the quality of any society depends on the quality of the people who built the society

5- According to Kent, in order to realize collective action in the social world, one must discover the laws of society, but Spencer says that we should not investigate laws to realize collective action, and sociologists should persuade people that society should not be subjected to government interference. and social reformers.

Some historians consider Spencer's sociology to be a continuation of Kent's organismic and evolutionary approach, but Spencer expresses his difference with Kent as follows:

"What is Kent's goal? Providing a coherent description of the progress of human concepts, but my goal is a coherent description of the progress of the external world. Kent's meaning is the necessary and real description of thoughts, but I, the real description of things, Kent's interpretation of the formation of natural knowledge, but I interpret the formation of phenomena that make up nature.

Spencer's most intense interest is evolutionary changes in social structures and institutions, not the mental states associated with these changes, in his opinion, thoughts are secondary phenomena.

But in the book of social sciences and its formation, Spencer is introduced as the one who used the ethnographic studies obtained by travelers and tourists for the first time in order to compare his social theories in different societies. to study

He divided the problems that exist in the study of social sciences into two types, visible and invisible. Spencer's acceptance of Lamarck's thought formed the basis of

his belief in compromise and adaptation and continuous progress. Spencer looks at the process of using Lamarck as the primary means of human biological and social adaptation. It is with the help of these means that people develop biologically, psychologically and socially, and human muscles and skills progress with use and non-use. Mental facilities related to understanding are developed through use and non-use, and social feelings related to cooperation, ethics and altruism are developed through the same process of use and non-use.

Spencer said: When the components of an organization become functionally specialized, these components must be increasingly coordinated with each other's activities, for example, groups that produce raw materials increasingly coordinate their activities with the demands of producers of finished products. These producers match their products with the demand of wholesalers who coordinate their purchases according to the needs of retailers and retailers adjust their purchases according to the needs of consumer groups.

In Spencer's methodology, he interpreted difference, specialization, and formation as a movement from uniformity without cohesion to organized difference. He recognized that traditions and group activities in different periods of life in different societies do not look completely the same, the differences are due to different levels of development or are related to certain environmental adaptations, although Spencer does not explicitly speak of cultural relativism, but when which argues that the characteristics of society should be considered in the context of society, confirms this trend.

Spencer never commented on the possibility that sociologists formulate their studies for the purpose of collecting data. In fact, Spencer's methodological rules for explaining and interpreting historical and ethnographic data prepared by others are used.

Among those who have been influenced by Spencer, we can mention Parnes, Habermas, Machiavelli, Pareto, Durkheim and even new theorists such as Sanderson and Liveries. Even his theories have had a great impact on the discussion of fascism and Nazism.

Robert J. Pirin distinguishes Spencer's four definitions of the concept of evolution from each other:

Evolution means human orientation towards an ideal social order.

Social evolution means differentiating between social groups in the form of functional micro-systems.

Social evolution means an increasing division of labor.

Social evolution means the growth of diversity in society in the sense that human society becomes more and more diverse.

These definitions have one thing in common and that is the transformation of unrelated homogeneous elements into heterogeneous ones.

For example, the evolution of a fragmented and fragmented society from a homogeneous feudal society to a heterogeneous but connected modern society.

The theory of social transformation

Spencer believed that all transformations - from the early cosmic transformations to the latest cultural results - reflect the transformation of homogeneous to heterogeneous in the process of evolution.

Spencer examined the concepts of institutions, structure and social function in the framework of his approach to social transformation.

The transformations within the structures lead to the change of their functions, in other words, the function of the whole depends on the function of the parts. Therefore, the more complex the whole becomes, the more the dependence between its parts increases, so that if the parts fall apart, the whole system will collapse. In this way, Spencer came up with the idea of society as an organism, without imagining the organism as a material or objective phenomenon. Three functional systems are particularly important in the evolution process:

food supply system or protection system, distribution system, and finally the regulatory system.

Society and involvement in its structure

By analyzing the process of social transformation, Spencer wanted to discover and explain the social order.

He understood society as a self-regulating social system that evolves in the process of continuous adaptation to the environment. He saw this process as an attempt to reach a new equilibrium, while this new equilibrium is also fluid, of course, in his opinion, there is also the possibility that this attempt will lead to stability and stagnation. Spencer was not trying to propose a theory about the stability of social structures. But he believed that social solidarity is conditional on the existence of a certain amount of certain general conditions. Unlike Marx and Kant, Spencer is not in favor of scientific intervention in social processes, but defends a theory that can be called paradoxical actionism, according to which social processes change based on specific laws, while the complexities of social actions and Problems caused by these complexities can lead to specific results. In order to prevent certain occurrences, sociology should avoid haste and thoughtless actions in its short-term plans.

The mutual correlation between social systems is so complex that the results of intervention cannot be predicted based on the map. Spencer, however, considered social changes to be a slow and gradual process that cannot be accelerated, but can be prevented. Social action pointed out and believes that any interference in the process of social change and development is dangerous and fruitless because the unforeseen results of interfering with the program in the complex set of the social system are always more than the predicted results of interfering with the program.

Military society and industrial society

Spencer drew a plan of the process of "evolution" of human societies with the two categories of "military society" and "industrial society". In his opinion, military societies are difficult and impossible in industrial societies. Military societies are human groups in which all people are military forces in times of war and war watchers in times of peace. Military societies usually have a moderate population with few internal differences. The survival of military societies depends on being able to spend a large portion of resources on military expenses. Military necessity requires such societies to have centralized power. Unlike military societies, industrial societies have many differences within themselves.

Government intervention in industrial societies, instead of voluntary agreement, necessarily leads to failure, because the free market determines the economic form with specific rules.

Unlike military societies, the social base in such societies is acquired and not appointed.

Trade and diplomacy, not military forces, are the factors that determine relations with other societies.

In the description of the industrial society, Spencer puts forward opinions that ultimately lead to the theory of the effect of interaction on human behavior.

Sociology

Spencer claimed that he was able to explain the past and future history of mankind with his sociology.

This claim is the logical result of accepting the diachronic perspective of history, based on which historical events are exclusive and unrepeatable and are caused by the impact of social forces.

The task of sociology in these conditions is to identify and determine these forces and to recognize and infer their direction of movement.

He could not substantiate his claim by gathering historical information. Spencer first stated the rules and claimed that these rules were true, then he collected data to prove his claims.

Organism theory

Contrary to the claims of many, Spencer did not consider society to be the same as organism. He believed that the only possible similarity between society and other things is the principled balance and regulation of their components. His purpose of comparing organism with society is simply to use the category of similarity as a heuristic tool. As he writes, the separate parts of animals are concrete and specific, therefore the whole animal is concrete, while the separate parts of society are abstract, so the whole society is concrete.

Effect on system theory

The new system theory also uses the category of organism as a research tool. System analysis is a suitable method to find out the general characteristics by examining specific cases. Since living systems, which are called organisms in Spencer's language, are open systems, their surrounding environment as well as the factors affecting the adaptation of their behavior must be determined.

Spencer came close to this system theory by proposing the mutual influence of society and its constituent units, which should pay attention to "the effect of the part on the whole" and "the effect of the whole on the part". Mutual influence is the basis of Spencer's sociology.

These comments are the first steps in the development of the new "general systems theory", which claims to have the most comprehensive theoretical and scientific framework.

System theory theorists are new scientific generalists who work with the same abstract models in various scientific fields.

Theory of social evolution and Herbert Spencer

evolution; Spencer says that evolution is "a change from a relatively indefinite, incoherent and homogeneous state to a relatively definite, coherent and diverse state"; And this evolution is actually the global process that explains both "the first transformations that the whole world must have seen" and "the last transformations that we find in society and the products of social life". He argues, as soon as this key is applied to the mysteries of the world, it becomes clear that the evolution of human societies, without being separated from other evolutionary phenomena, is nothing but a special case of natural law that has universal application. Spencer, society is an organism. Communities and living organisms follow similar laws of development. This is the characteristic of social organisms, which, like living organisms, become larger structurally when they grow physically. Like lower animals, the human embryo also has several specific parts, but when the embryo grows, its organs increase and each one does something separately. The same is true of society. At first, the dissimilarity among its groups is imperceptible in terms of number and degree, but when the population increases, the dissimilarity and separation also increases. Spencer considered the evolution of society as the result

of political and regional conflicts. And in fact, he was one of the first sociologists who understood the importance of war and conflict in the internal patterns of social organization of a society. According to Spencer, evolution occurs due to the inherent instability of cohesive masses, and because forces push elements in different directions, their separation in diverse environments will lead to differences between elements that adapt themselves to different realms. . unilinear or multilinear evolution; In the discussion of the evolution of society, sociologists generally believed in two types of evolution:

A) Single-line evolution, which has a longer history, is based on the fact that all human societies go through certain and unavoidable stages, and the transition from each stage to another is regular, and the stages must be passed in order, and in Undoubtedly, all human societies will pass this way.

b) Theory of multi-line evolution: some believe that societies can go through different paths, another group says that societies have traveled the path of modernity, but with ups and downs and sometimes even going back and forth, that is, sometimes societies are possible. Regressive garlic have or go to decline. Spencer believes that just as there is no shortcut in the path of growth from childhood to adulthood, which can be freed from the long process of growth and evolution through unreasonable leaps, for the lower forms of social life, except through small and fundamental transformations. There is no other way to reach the top. Especially in his early writings, Spencer depicts the process of evolution as an unstoppable, restless and continuously active dynamic.

Spencer, at the age of Kamal, perhaps under the influence of despair caused by the collectivist path that British society took at the end of the 19th century, recognized that although the overall evolution of mankind is certain, in this process, some societies may regress and Others progress.

He believed that there is a possibility of a society's regression as well as its progress. Although Spencer is generally considered to be a staunch evolutionist, this impression is not absolutely acceptable. During his intellectual maturity, he had come to the opinion that a society may regress instead of progress and go back. Unlike Comte, Spencer did not believe that societies progress through certain

predetermined stages. Rather, in his opinion, societies evolve or freeze in response to their social and natural environment. Spencer considered evolution and effort to be related processes. Society falls apart when it stops progressing. He considered society without progress to be doomed to decline. If a society is located in the vicinity of societies that are evolving, but this society itself does not evolve, it will not be able to compete and faces the risk of being captured and conquered by more advanced societies. According to Spencer, human history is evolutionary history as a whole. Although there have been societies that have turned backwards and disintegrated after progressing. Spencer argued that a social organism, like an individual organism, can change so much to achieve equilibrium with its environmental conditions, but after that it can continue to live without accepting any further changes in its structure. Spencer was more of the opinion that there is no need for societies to evolve through predetermined and irreversible stages, rather societies evolve by reacting to their social and natural environment. Spencer says: Social progress, like other types of progress, is not a single line, but has various paths ahead. Mankind, which is scattered all over the earth, has faced various environments, and in each of these cases, a part of his social life has been affected by the previous social life and another part has been affected by the new environment. From his point of view, the truth is that different social groups do not form a connected field like the types of individual organisms, but they can only be classified as different groups.

development; Inspired by biology and Darwin's theories, Spencer proposed the idea of "organismal evolution" as the gradual progress of social life from simple forms to complex forms, from initial homogeneity to increasing heterogeneity, and he intended to apply the laws of "inbreeding" to human societies. According to Spencer, evolution is the integration and integration of matter, which is accompanied by friction and separation of motion. During this process, matter passes from the state of indeterminate and chaotic homogeneity or homogeneity to the state of determinate and regular multiplicity, meanwhile, the stopped motion also undergoes the same change and transformation. He believed that societies evolve and develop based on natural laws, and it is this evolution that leads to the survival of the stronger element.

social development; According to Spencer, both organic collections and social collections are characterized by their ever-increasing volume. which some of them

will reach in the future, are very small. Social growth can be achieved through two processes that are sometimes separate from each other and sometimes combined

This growth is either due to an increase in the population or by "simple reproduction of units" or by the joining of units that had no connection with each other before, that is, by "unification of groups and again by the union of groups of groups" ". The increase in the volume of the units is accompanied by an increase in the complexity of their structure. According to Spencer, the process of growth is basically a process of integration, and integration, in turn, must be accompanied by the differentiation of structures and functions as much as possible, otherwise, the organism or social unit cannot survive in the struggle for survival.

Like organic collections, social collections begin their growth from relatively undifferentiated states in which the components of a collection are similar to each other; Then they reach distinct states in which only the parts are dissimilar to each other. But although the parts are different from each other, they are still dependent on each other. Therefore, increasing differentiation is accompanied by increasing interdependence and integration of components. In parallel, the components of a social whole become more dissimilar and the roles of individuals become different, their interdependence also increases. In evolved collections, it is the combination of the actions of the parts that makes the life of the whole and enables the continuation of the life of the parts. As a result, when the components have a little difference from each other, they can perform each other's functions easily, while if the components are sufficiently differentiated from each other, they cannot perform their tasks well or at all. They are not able to do such a thing. Therefore, the structure of complex societies is more vulnerable and fragile than the structure of older and simpler societies.

norms and social structures; From the historical point of view, in his analysis, Spencer divided societies into two methods: "macro" and "micro". At first glance, he divided societies into two types: "warrior" and "industrial".

Warrior Society:

Conflict relations between it and neighboring societies should be based on the originality of out-group conflict.

The government is omnipotent.

The number of public social organizations and institutions is more than private organizations and institutions.

The principle of centralization is strictly observed. There is forced cooperation (such as subordination of external body parts to the central nervous system).

Blind information, pure obedience to leadership power, having national prejudice and lack of vertical social mobility.

Societies are subject to the government's will, and forceful supervision dominates the society.

Division of society into military ranks.

The external adjuster dominates the internal retainer.

Industrious or industrial society:

Internal regulatory systems are relatively weak and scattered.

The special industry of these societies is voluntary cooperation and individual self-restraint.

The main regulatory body of decentralized society and individual power is taken from different classes of society.

Outgroup conflict is curbed by peaceful behavior.

The relationship between people and the government is voluntary cooperation.

The principle of individual freedom is respected and freedom of opinion and religion.

The role of the government has been established as an observer and supporter of people's social and economic rights, and its goal is to protect the rights of individuals.

No class gap.

The existence of private and charitable organizations.

Election of the government by the people.

He understood the evolutionary process towards industrial societies. For him, the industrial society contained all the ideals he nurtured in his mind. In industrial societies, the increase in volume, complexity, specialization and interdependencies of components in social organisms ultimately led to more order and less need for "external regulators" (use of state force, police) was felt, which is the same. It made possible the areas of increasing individual freedoms, reducing government intervention and the emergence of a democratic society, although he was concerned with the strong dependence that exists between parts in such societies, in such a way that damage to one area affects the entire organism. He considered it more fragile than the previous societies and was worried about this.

In fact, in industrial societies, Spencer's focus on the social organism and the dependence of the parts in this organism on each other drew him towards a functionalist view, although his emphasis on the individual and the possibility of his awareness in the social organism separated him from other functionalists such as Comte and Durkheim separated. Spencer used the difference in social organization caused by social regulation as the basis of his work to separate the societies that he called the warrior society and the industrial society. Spencer emphasized that the degree of social complexity is independent of the separation of societies into two types of warrior and industrial societies. In this sense, relatively undifferentiated societies can also be "industrial" (though not in the modern sense of "industrial society"), and new complex societies can also be warlike. What makes a society industrial or warlike is its level of sophistication. It is not, but the presence or absence of conflict with neighbors is the determining factor here. Spencer's famous genealogy calls societies military and industrial. Therefore, both very simple societies and very new societies can be military or industrial. His other genealogy searches for the description of separate stages of long-term social development. This genealogy revolves around the description of patterns and directions of social segregation. This classification is based on a social theory that says that the types of social structures depend on the neighborhood relationship of a society with other societies, which divides societies into two categories: warrior and hard working or industrial. The classification and separation of warrior and industrial societies is based on social regulation and differences in social organization. Therefore, the peaceful or hostile nature of this relationship affects the internal structures of a society and its social regulation system. In peaceful relations, internal regulation

systems are relatively weak and scattered, but in conflict relations, centralized and forceful supervisions rule the society. The distinguishing feature of the warrior structure is that its constituent units are "forced" to adopt common actions. Unlike the warrior society, the industrial society is based on voluntary cooperation and individual self-restraint. This system tends to decentralize the main regulatory body of the society and take its power from different classes of the society.

But in the direction of wisdom, Spencer divided the types of societies according to their evolutionary stages and their structural complexity into "simple, mixed, double mixed and extreme mixed" societies. His terms in this context are somewhat vague, but what he had in mind was a kind of classification according to the degree of structural complexity. To put it more precisely, Spencer distinguished between simple societies that did not have a leader, societies that had temporary leadership, and societies that had a permanent leadership institution. Mixed and double mixed societies were also classified according to the complexity of their political organization.

Simple societies

In a simple society, there is a totality in which nothing is dependent on another, and its components, with or without the presence of a regulating center (central leader) in line with common goals (such as gathering food, and meeting other basic needs) cooperate and participate with each other and there is a low level of difference, specialization and independence of vote (as in early communes

Mixed societies

Mixed societies consist of two or more simple societies that are mostly engaged in agriculture and sometimes may be violent or peaceful and organized spiritual groups are observed in it (such as tribal societies

Double or dual composite societies

But in mixed societies, the population is completely settled, there are stronger customs and social customs, they have a larger and more specific political structure, and there are religious hierarchies, class distinctions, and a more complicated division of labor among them. like medieval Europe). The following are the characteristics of double hybrid societies:

functionalism; Spencer emphasized that the transformation in the structure cannot occur without the transformation in the function and the increase in the size of social units will necessarily lead to the increasing differentiation in social activities. In fact, most of Spencer's discussion about social institutions and their transformations is expressed in functional terms. In these analyses, Spencer often begins his work by looking for functions, each of which is made for a special task. "In order to understand how an organization was born and developed, it is necessary to understand what needs this organization had to fulfill in the beginning and later." Spencer provided comprehensive descriptions of the construction, function, and evolutionary transformation of six basic institutions. These six important institutions are: family, social, political, ecclesiastical, professional and political institutions. He analyzed social institutions in relation to the public context in which these institutions were placed in various ways. Spencer stated that customs that are strange and ugly according to contemporary standards should not be considered as having no value for certain societies. In other words, what A From the point of view of our feelings and thoughts, it is adjusted in the worst way, it was very appropriate for those situations where better adjustments were not practical. Spencer has benefited from functionalist terms in the discussions related to social institutions and their changes. In discussing social institutions, Spencer tried hard to show that these institutions are not the result of the stability and intentional motivations of social actors, but rather originate from functional requirements and structural requirements. Therefore, the reasons for considering Spencer to be functionalist can be mentioned as follows:

- 1- It considers all the parts of existence as small elements that interact with each other to maintain the system and move towards the overall goals of that system.
- 2- To understand any social issue, we must know the function of social construction.
- 3- individualism; Spencer, while evolutionism, is an individualist sociologist who has an extreme individualistic position regarding the relationship between the individual and the society, in his opinion, the individual has a superior position and the society should not interfere with the movement and freedom of the individual because all individual behaviors that are directed towards personal interests, In fact, it also works for the benefit of the society. Unlike Comte, he thought about the origin

of society with individualistic and utilitarian categories and saw society as a circle to advance people's goals. According to him, humans were originally connected to each other because they saw that this connection was beneficial to them. "Social life was born from the fact that for the majority of people this kind of life was more beneficial than the isolated life of an individual.

So, according to Spencer, with the formation of society, people are involved in a complex relationship, and this conflict does not mean removing and digesting people in the society. The social organism not only does not prevent the sub-division of components or their interrelationship with each other, but also maintains their harmony. In his opinion, clothing exists to serve its members, not to serve the society. As the components of the society are more differentiated from each other, the roles of people are also more differentiated and their interdependence increases. While in simple societies one component can replace another component, this is not possible in more complex societies.

the principle of non-interference in laws; Spencer, like Kent, had a stubborn belief in the functioning of social laws, and like Kent, he believed that these laws are forced like the laws governing nature. "There is no other way. Society either has rules or it doesn't. If society does not have laws, neither order, nor certainty, nor order can exist in social phenomena.

If the society has rules, these rules should also be like other rules of Gati; Inflexible, even more active and unexceptional". But unlike Kent, who emphasized that humans should try to discover the laws of society in order to realize collective action in the social world, Spencer argued with the same stubbornness that we should not examine these laws to realize collective action. Kent, who wanted to directly guide society through the spiritual power of sociologist priests, Spencer argued that sociologists should convince people that society should not be subject to the interference of governments and social reformers. Considering the complexities of the causes operating in society and the fact that human actions may lead to unforeseen results, Spencer insists on letting things take their natural course. The only power that Spencer attributed to the government was It was protecting the rights of individuals and collective protection of society against foreign enemies. According to Spencer, a good society is based on contracts that are made between individuals pursuing their own interests. If the government intervenes in these

contractual arrangements due to social welfare, it will either disrupt the social order or cause humans to be deprived of the benefits of the industrial society and return to the previous forms of violent or warlike social order. Theory Spencer's anti-collectivism was based on the "survival of the fittest" religion. Spencer's most important contribution to the development of sociology should be considered in the design of the concept of survival of the fittest. Spencer proposed this concept about ten years before the publication of Darwin's ideas about natural selection. Darwin later said that he essentially preferred Spencer's term survival of the fittest to his own term natural selection.

According to Spencer, the evolution of biological species and social species is basically related to the survival of the fittest. According to this thinking, evolutionary processes purge unsuitable species. And the final result will be the formation of a more complete society. Spencer, who saw this result as a result of natural processes, was a staunch supporter of the free economy or policy of non-intervention. Consistency is the key to this process. People must change with the changes. In this theory, Spencer argued that any increase in human fertility would also stimulate more activity, because the larger the population, the more intelligence is needed to survive. The least intelligent groups and individuals One after the other, they will die, and in this way, the general level of intelligence will gradually and inevitably rise. Spencer said that the general level of intelligence will rise so much that only those with superior intelligence can survive the battle for survival. in the brand. He believed that if the government intervenes in the work of this beneficial mechanism by imposing welfare laws and does not allow the beneficial processes of natural selection to do their work well, this beneficial mechanism will be fatally damaged. Spencer argued that government intervention in social affairs disrupts the necessary adaptation of society to its environment. principles of system growth and separation; Spencer observed a fundamental relationship in the social world between size and social density and the process of structural segregation. and presented this view in the analogy of "growth". With the conclusion that segregation in social systems is a positive function of the increase in the size of social density. And through this analogy of growth, he articulated other correlations. Growth rate and degree of concentration of community members during growth depend on structural segregation. However, he observed that growth in the size of a system depends, to a large extent, on previous growth in the size and level of segregation in a community.

conclusion

According to the mentioned contents, it can be said that two issues are mixed in Spencer's theories:

- 1- Evolutionary stages mentioned in biology
- 2- Changes and transformations of human society throughout history

And Spencer's work is important in his era in two ways:

- 1- Solving the problem of the relationship between philosophy and empirical sciences and defining philosophy as a unifying knowledge that curbs the fragmentation and over-specialization of sciences.
- 2- Presenting a practical theory about the phenomenon of development, especially social and historical development. Spencer refers to the word "community" to a group of people whose distribution of parts has a special durability and consistency and their lives are fixed in a specific place.

In Spencer's opinion, society is a superior organ that is obtained from the combination of individual organs, and culture in its modern sense is seen as a system of mutual relations of actions and thoughts in his writings. He compares the society to a living body that has parts and accessories. In his opinion, the whole society has a certain function in such a way that he compares the government to the head, the army and economic activities to other organs, and he thinks of human communities as a living organism that is growing and evolving.

He does not consider the evolution of society to be dependent on one factor, but believes that the path of evolution is determined by an unknown force and there is no single determining factor to explain the changes and transformations of society. Spencer was of the opinion that change and transformation in society is based on unanticipated results and in sync with expected results, and this has made complete planning impossible. He draws parallels between the growth of organic collections and social collections:

- 1- Both start their growth from an undifferentiated state.

2- First, the components of a set are similar to each other, then they become distinct and dissimilar.

3- Social and organic collections are interdependent.

4- Increasing differentiation is associated with increasing interdependence and integration of components.

5- Both movements are on the path of growth and development.

6- Both expand in size, dimensions, complexity and increase in efficiency They have a choice.

7- The division of duties between the components of both is completely evident.

He distinguishes between social and biological organism, including:

The parts of the organism form a unified whole, but the parts of society form a separate whole.

The units that make up the organism are attached to each other, but the units of the society are free and scattered.

Coherence between the parts of the organism is necessary and essential, but the parts do not form a unified society.

The components of the social organism can influence each other through mediators such as language.

The exchange of messages in the organism is through physical stimulation, but in the society, the exchange of messages is through language and emotion.

In an organism, consciousness is concentrated in a small part, but in a society, consciousness is scattered throughout the complex.

There are physical nerves in the organism, but in society, the welfare of the whole cannot be separate from the welfare of its constituent units.

Body parts are alive by means of nerves (center), but society exists for its members.

The members of the organism are all involved in the same news, but the members of the society have relative independence.

The complete lack of coordination between the components of the social organism.

Each component of a social system has its own perception and emotional sensitivities, which causes discretion and differences in their actions.

It is the independence of opinion and sensory differences in human emotional perception that, unlike the components in the organism, can bring relatively significant changes in one's life.

Biological entities have specific, fixed and visible external forms, while society does not have such a form.

The units of a biological entity are physically related to each other, while the members of a community may be scattered in a wide area and not have direct contact with each other.

The parts of an organism are stable and stable in terms of their position relative to each other, while the people of a society do not necessarily live in one place and are able to move from one point to another and rearrange their spatial relationships.

Self-awareness is located in only one part of biological existence (in the brain), while every person in society is capable of having independent self-awareness.

Spencer was influenced by the views of the evolutionists of his time such as Darwin, Lamarck, on the one hand, was influenced by the opinions of demographers such as Malton, and established the foundation of his social philosophy. By proposing the principle of "survival conflict", Malthus considers the society as a battlefield in which people are engaged in war and conflict to obtain the means of life. Spencer puts this principle together with Darwin's principle of "natural selection" as the basis

of his social theories and proposes the principle of "persistence of the fittest" or "survival of the fittest".

Spencer's belief in the survival of Islam was that as the population increases, it needs more intelligence to survive, so the least intelligent groups and individuals will die, and as a result, the general level of intelligence will gradually and inevitably be high, so only those with superior intelligence will survive. They can survive the battle for survival.

His famous book "Composite Philosophy" has planned the construction of an ideal society based on the principle of free competition and the principle of compatibility and natural selection. He proposed to dissolve all the institutions that hinder the flow of rational and natural laws. Societies, like other parts of existence, are subject to natural laws, and the principle of natural selection is dominant and suitable for the continuation of life, therefore, any interference in internal affairs and any type of activity that aims to support the weak and the poor is rejected due to the disruption of natural laws. and it not only leads to deviation and disorder, but also causes the degeneration and destruction of societies. Man has no role in Spencer's sociological system except as a functional factor.

Spencer believed that the application of severe restrictions and direct measures in the society will not result in the desired recovery and reform, therefore, he considers the role of reforming individuals and movements to be very insignificant in changing the path of society's development. According to Spencer, society is an entity with its own special structure and with organs and members that are responsible for each specific function, and it is the maintenance of these functions that makes the system and the overall structure of society possible for growth and expansion, because the growth and expansion of societies It is the result of more structure and separation of duties between organs.

Complexity in roles and increased functional separation from Spencer's meeting is one of the most important criteria for the progress of societies. Spencer's basic processes of growth, differentiation, integration and adaptive improvement are to some extent conditioned by factors:

External factors such as access to natural resources

Internal factors such as the nature of internal units

He knew concrete factors such as the existence of other societies with internal values and beliefs.

Spencer defines the members of the society in terms of social traits as:

King: A practical example of the power of nature, which is summed up in the power of the king.

The king's advisors who have the task of providing intellectual advice.

The majority of people who have the duty to obey the king and fulfill their duties.

Spencer defines three types of government:

Monarchy: Although it is bad, it is the most practical form of government, because if society is ruled by force, all members act based on it, so a king is necessary to reduce the difference in procedure (it is the best type of government).

Oligarchy or Ishraqi: Democracy and democrats: because it requires consciousness and awareness to some extent, and people's consciousness and awareness are not yet developed, so democracy cannot be suitable for current societies. He considers the mental and psychological characteristics and behavioral capabilities of the people of each society to be influenced by the degree of influence of the government and the way it deals with out-group conflict and practically the social structure of each of these two types of society, so that ultimately two types of social relations result. gives:

Relationships based on coercion and imposition

Relationships based on voluntary cooperation and based on social contracts. Spencer accepted the negative performance of some elements in society, but he believed that society as a whole exists in a state of functional interaction. The word "equilibrium" in Spencer's words does not refer to a static state, but refers to a dynamic process. Spencer divides the functional groups of society into three devices:

A holding or internal device that is related to the production of goods.

The regulatory or external body that is responsible for establishing political order and organizing the military machine of the society.

The distribution device that connects the setting device and the maintenance device is like the communication channels in the society.

Spencer believes that the duty of the government is to control and properly implement the laws. Therefore, one of the functions of the government can be considered as reducing intra-group conflict and increasing the spirit of cooperation in society. The only power that Spencer has given to the government is to protect people's rights and protect against foreign enemies, the rest of the affairs should be left to the free initiative of the people of the society so that they can organize their lives through contracts and mutual agreements. He considers political as the interdependence of dissimilar parts in complex societies and the fragility resulting from it, which requires a regulatory system to monitor the actions of the parts of society and ensure harmony between them. Political organs, like living organs, inevitably have a system. It is a regulator at the beginning of the process of social evolution, the regulatory centers were for communication with the external environment, such as enemies, animals, and hunting, but with the progress of the evolution of these centers, they take on the task of regulating internal affairs and social supervision. Spencer's most intense interest is evolutionary transformations. It is in the social structures and institutions, not the mental states associated with these transformations, in his opinion, the thoughts are secondary phenomena. He used and introduced the obtained social theories so that he could study his social theories in different societies from a comparative point of view. He divided the problems in the study of social sciences into two types, visible and invisible. He considered the complexity of the studied issues and invisible problems to be related to the spirit and way of thinking of the examiners. Spencer's acceptance of Lamarck's thought formed the basis of his belief in compromise and adaptation and continuous progress. Spencer looked at the process of using Lamarck as the primary means of human biological and social adaptation. It is with the help of these means that people develop biologically, psychologically and socially, muscles and human skills progress with the use and non-use of mental facilities. Related to understanding and understanding, they develop through use and disuse, and social feelings related to cooperation, ethics, and altruism progress through the same process of use and disuse.

In Spencer's methodology, he interpreted difference, specialization, and development as a movement from uniformity without coherence to organized

difference. He recognized that traditions and group activities in different periods of life in different societies do not look completely the same, the differences are due to different levels of development or are related to certain environmental adaptations, although Spencer does not explicitly speak of cultural relativism. But when he argues that the characteristics of society should be matched in the context of society, he confirms this tendency.

Spencer never commented on the possibility that sociologists formulate their studies for the purpose of collecting data. In fact, Spencer's methodological rules for explaining and interpreting historical and ethnographic data prepared by others are used. Parsons, Habermas, Machiavelli, Pareto, Durkheim, and even new theorists such as Sanderson and Liferies can be mentioned among those who were influenced by Spencer.

Jean Baptiste Lamarck

(in French: Jean-Baptiste Lamarck) with the full name Jean-Baptiste Pierre Antoine de Monet Chevalier de la Marck (in French: Jean-Baptiste Pierre Antoine de Monet, Chevalier de la Marck) a soldier, biologist, academic and one of the first who suggested that the evolution of living things is continuous and is based on natural laws. He is the exponent of Lamarckism. When he was forced to leave the army due to illness, he wanted to study medicine, but his financial situation did not allow him, but he fell in love with botany and worked in a bank in Paris. He married four times, but death did not allow any of his wives. He became blind eleven years before his death. One of his sons was deaf and the other was insane. Lamarck was partially recognized by the French scientific community through Buffon's efforts. Lamarck stated two theories of the use and non-use of organs and the heredity of acquired traits to explain how evolution occurs. He observed that if an organ of the body of an organism is used, it becomes bigger and more efficient, and if an organ is not used, it shrinks and decays; Therefore, as a result of inconsistency in the use and non-use of different body parts during a person's life, the organism may change to some extent and acquire some characteristics. Lamarck considered such acquired traits to be hereditary and transferable to offspring. This theory was very successful and helped spread the idea of evolution. But finally it turned out that Lamarck's opinion was wrong. It is true that the use and non-use of organs leads to the acquisition of an attribute; But Lamarck's mistake was that, contrary to his opinion,

acquired traits are not inherited. One attempt to invalidate Lamarckism was a famous experiment by 19th-century biologist August Weissmann, who showed that breeding mice with their tails cut off produced mice with normal tails; In this experiment, he cut off the tails of newborn mice as soon as they were born, with the conclusion that the absence and use of tails in mice will cause this trait to disappear in the next generation of mice. He continued this experiment until the 20th generation of mice. (he cut off the tail of 20 generations of newborn mice), but contrary to the imagination, the tail of mice not only disappeared He went, but he was not even smaller.

The theory of evolution

Later, the theory of evolution was developed by Darwin; In his theory, he stated that existing traits are created as a result of mutation (just like the malformed children that are born from humans), and if these new traits that are created as a result of mutation are harmful to the organism, the generation of organisms with this trait will decrease. But if these mutated traits are beneficial and useful for the organism and help the organism to survive in harsh and unsuitable environments, the generation of organisms with these traits will increase, while the organisms that lack this trait will eventually die and their generation will decrease.

Lamarckism

According to Lamarck (1744-1829) and many biologists at the same time as him and after him, various factors that affect a person during his life also affect the nature of his children. This view, which is known today as Lamarckism or Lamarckism, is now completely obsolete. Lamarckists believed that if an organ is used a lot, that organ will gradually strengthen and obtain a new form suitable to the habit it has acquired. For example, therefore, the neck and legs of the giraffe were elongated in the same way. On the other hand, if an organ is not used, that organ gradually decays and shrinks, until it may be completely lost. According to Lamarck, the lack of eyes in the creatures living in dark caves or the lack of arms and legs in snakes was for this reason. Lamarck believed in the heredity of acquired traits. According to him, all the changes that appear in the structure of people due to acquisition (compromise) during the life period, are preserved during reproduction and transferred to the next generations; For example, the children of a blacksmith will have strong arms because their father has done a lot of work with his arms. This principle is the most

famous principle in Lamarck's theory, which led to the popularization of Lamarxism.

Rejection of Lamarckism

Contrary to the opinion of Lamarck and his associates, today we know that acquired traits are not inherited, because they are caused by the effects of the environment and the growth of the organism, not the effects of the genes of the organism. Only traits dependent on genes can be passed from one generation to the next generation, provided that the genes controlling those traits are present in "sex" cells (gametes). Any changes that occur as a result of using or not using organs, or for any other reason, in other cells of the body, other than sex cells, will not affect the characteristics of the next generation. Many experiments have been done in this field; For example, to test the effect of not using an organ, an experiment was arranged in which flies mated for 69 generations in the dark. At the end, it was observed that the vision of the last generation was not damaged and the reaction of its individuals in front of light was completely normal.

Early history

Inheritance of acquired characteristics was proposed in ancient times and remained a common idea for many centuries. The historian Kenway Zirke wrote in 1935 that:

(The old and rejected theory of heredity) Darwin's theory of pangenesis

Charles Darwin's *On the Origin of Species* proposed natural selection as the primary mechanism for the development of species, but did not reject a form of Lamarckism as the mechanism of segregation.

Lamarck's evolutionary framework

Between 1800 and 1830, Lamarck provided a systematic theoretical framework for understanding evolution. He considered evolution to consist of four laws: "Life itself tends to increase in volume all the organs which have life-force, and the life-force expands their dimensions to such an extent that those parts become like themselves." "The production of a new part in the animal body is caused by new needs that arise and continue until that part itself has a feeling and produces a new movement that is needed in the transfer to the next generation and its provision and continuation." "The growth of the organs and their ability is permanently the result of their use of

those organs." "It is conveyed that it is related to those who have gone through these changes."

Lamarck's discussion of heredity

In 1830, apart from the evolutionary framework, Lamarck briefly mentioned two old ideas in his discussion of heredity. These ideas were considered completely correct in their time. The first idea was the idea of using heredity against diseases. He proposed that people lose traits they don't use or traits they don't need to have, and on the other hand, they expand traits that are useful.

Weissman's test

The idea that germ-line cells contain information that is not influenced through experience and independently of somatic (body) cells, these are known as cords because this makes Lamarck's theory of inheritance of variation in the body a matter difficult or even impossible.

Neo-Lamarckism

The period in the history of evolutionary thought between the death of Darwin in the 1880s and the foundation of population genetics in the 1920s and the beginning of the modern evolutionary synthesis in the 1930s is called by some historians the eclipse of Darwinism.

19th century

Neomarcian versions of evolution were widespread in the late 19th century. The belief that living things can to some extent choose the characteristics they inherit allowed them to be at the mercy of the environment, contrary to Darwinian theory.

early 20th century

A century after Lamarck, scientists and philosophers continued to search for mechanisms and evidence for traits required for heredity. Sometimes some experiments were reported to be successful, but from the beginning, this was either always criticized or the basis of the work was known to be false and impure.

Late 20th century

English anthropologist Frederick Wood Jones and South African paleontologist Robert Broom supported the neo-Lamarckian view of human evolution. German anthropologist Hermann Klatsch tried to explain the origin of amphipods using the neo-Lamarckian evolutionary model.

2009, 150 years after the publication of Darwin's book *Origin of Species*, became an excuse to commemorate Charles Robert Darwin (1829-1882) and his intellectual legacy; But the year 2009 also had another historical echo: the 200th anniversary of the publication of the book *Philosophy of Zoology* by Jean-Baptiste Pierre-Antoine de Monet Chevalier de Lamarck (1744-1829) (Figure 1). Contrary to Darwin's thoughts, which eventually led to the birth of evolutionary biology and is the only accepted approach to scientifically justify the transformation of living organisms throughout the history of life on this planet, the word Lamarckism basically had no place in current biology until recently. In recent years, however, a new spirit has been breathed into the word Lamarckism, and it has been covered by the name of neo-Marxism. What did Lamarck say is needed now again?

Many consider Lamarck's theory as a theory of heredity and think that he is the creator of the inheritance of acquired traits. Lamarck himself, referring to the inheritance of the traits acquired by the parent during his lifetime and passed on to the next generation, says: "The natural law according to which offspring inherit all the makeup acquired during the lifetime of their parents is so true and clear. And there is such evidence that no observer has been unable to convince himself of the correctness of this law" (quoted from *Natural History of Invertebrates* 2, 1815). This "law" of heredity was so accepted that heredity in Darwin's evolutionary theory, until the publication of his genetic theory in the form of his other great work, *The Diversity of Plants and Animals Under Domestication* (1868), was defined in the framework of this accepted model of the transmission of traits from parents to offspring. In fact, Lamarckism was a theory indicating the change and transformation of organisms, like Darwin's theory, but it had fundamental differences.

Since its publication, Lamarck's zoological philosophy has not had the same fortune as the origin of species; This work was not translated into English until 105 years after its publication, while only 77 years were needed for the publication of the Ukrainian version of Darwin's work. The language of zoological philosophy

is a tangled and ambiguous language, and it is not easy to extract Lamarck's basic thought from the pages of this book. Graer et al.⁴ believe that some of the foundations of Darwinism can be extracted from Lamarck's prose; Thoughts such as the gradual transformation of species, the slowness of the evolution process, the occurrence of evolution due to compromise with the environment, the tendency of this process to create more complex forms and the idea that living organisms are related to each other.

Lamarckism versus Darwinism

The fact that we don't know Lamarck because of these revolutionary thoughts, but consider his entire evolutionary theory to be a caricature of Darwinism, has several main reasons: Georges Cuvier, one of the most prominent naturalists of Lamarck's time, was strongly against Lamarck's evolutionary theory, and even in his obituary Writing about Lamarck's death, he wrote that Lamarck's thinking "doesn't last a moment against the scrutiny of someone who has dissected a hand, an internal organ, or even a fairy." Darwin was deeply disturbed by comparing the overlapping parts of his evolutionary theory with Lamarck's thoughts. Even in the early stages of Darwin's evolutionary theory, late 1837 and early 1838, Darwin wrote in his personal notebook: "My theory is different from Lamarck's theory"⁷. Although the theories of Darwin and Lamarck can be considered evolutionary; But Darwin, unlike Lamarck, did not at all believe in the innate progress of organisms towards more complex forms; For Darwin, life remains a tree; But Lamarck's view was more ladder-like. A much more fundamental difference between Lamarck's and Darwin's views can be found in the role that Darwin attributed to chance in evolution. The adaptation of organisms to the environment is much more straightforward from Lamarck's point of view than from Darwin's point of view:

A shorebird that does not like to swim, but needs to get close to the water to find prey, is always prone to sinking into the swamp; But the desire to behave in such a way as not to drown in the water makes him accustomed to stretching and elongating his legs. Such a habit over generations in these birds, who take this procedure in life, leads to people who are on stilts - that is, long bare legs.

Darwin did not believe in such a transformative process at all; From Darwin's point of view, what is described as the adaptation of organisms to the environment is the result of screening, not the transformation of the living organism. In other words,

the compromise process in the framework of Darwinism requires diversity; But the Lamarckian adaptation process does not require any genetic and phenotypic variation. From Lamarck's point of view, the living being is more like play dough that can be transformed into any shape due to the desire to change. Such a difference was extremely troublesome for Darwin; Apart from the fact that it was difficult to explain the existence of diversity in the absence of a reasonable model to justify the inheritance of traits and why the difference between parents and children, it was very difficult for Darwin's contemporaries to attribute the emergence of a part of this diversity to luck, as it is even in our era. It is also very difficult for many people, including a number of scientists, to accept the random nature of some natural phenomena. The heredity model that Darwin presented in the diversity of plants and animals under domestication enumerates two categories of reasons for diversity in biological populations: firstly, the lack, increase and transfer of hereditary elements and the second is the direct effect of environmental conditions and the use or non-use of organs on these elements. .

The modern meaning of Lamarckism

According to the above descriptions, Lamarckism was not presented by Lamarck as a model of heredity in any way; Rather, it was the first evolutionary theory to describe the diversity and adaptation of living organisms. But why is this Lamarckism revived in our time? In the book *Lamarck's Revenge*¹³, Peterward can hardly accept the prospect of the revival of Lamarckism and is waiting for a fundamental revolution in biology. It is a fascinating story that Lamarck, after years of relative obscurity compared to Darwin, found his life again and abandoned Darwinism; We all love stories in which people who were ridiculed and wronged, have once again achieved fame and doubled their reputation; But Lamarckism and Darwinism are not characters in a story or TV series, the question is the scientific validity of this apparent controversy.

Current debates surrounding Lamarckism mostly revolve around epigenetics. At the beginning, epigenetics had a fundamentally different meaning from our current understanding, and it was related to the development of the living organism against the ancient view of epigenetics in A. This was the platform for the development of an organism from an egg cell to a complete organism by passing through embryonic stages. Pre-formationists, however, believed that a miniature version of the creature

resided inside the egg and simply grew larger over time. Conrad Waddington, a British evolutionist, geneticist and philosopher gave a new meaning to epigenetics. Waddington turned epigenetics into a branch of biology that studies the causal relationship between genes and the products of these genes and the resulting phenotype. In his book *The Strategy of Genes*, Waddington proposes the concept of the epigenetic landscape, which depicts the different paths that the same genetic information can lead to. Our current understanding of such a picture is practically the interaction of genes that leads to the production of different phenotypes, without the need to change genetic information.

such interactions and information that are not in the form of genetic information; But they are partly heritable, it has become very hot; But why should these thoughts be called Lamarckism? It does not seem that the inheritance of acquired traits in its new form, that is, the inheritance of epigenetic information seen in the form of changes in the methylation patterns of histones, has much to do with Lamarckism. Both Lamarck and Darwin benefited from the popular model of heredity in their time, and Lamarck was not the originator of the inheritance of acquired traits. At the same time, it seems a bit strange to call epigenetic findings revolutionary in its current form; Because, firstly, Darwinism is not based on the genetic nature of heredity; Rather, it simply requires some kind of inheritance and a mechanism to produce heritable diversity, whether this diversity is from DNA or the methylation patterns of histones; Secondly, epigenetic inheritance is basically impossible without genetics, and based on studies that have investigated the role of epigenetic changes in the adaptation of organisms, such changes are only effective in the short term and must lead to genetic changes in order to survive. Words in science have their own meanings, and attaching Lamarckism to epigenetic studies at best leads to misleading scientists and at worst leads to cynicism. What is needed is simply the acceptance of a simple definition of heritable information and not Lamarck's revolutionary claim in biology.

Evolutionary theories (Darwinism and Lamarckism)

Order:

In the three main phenomena of life (nutrition, communication and reproduction), a very precise order is observed. Performing the vital actions of a cell or a multicellular organism or a plant always flows with a certain order. The interactions and interactions inside the protoplasm of every living cell have a unique synchronization and coordination, and also all the chemical reactions of life are carried out with the help of enzymes, which are actually a type of catalyst, considering that each enzyme catalyzes a specific reaction, so The series of reactions happens one after the other and regularly. This order can never be a product of chance or accident. According to the above, it can be seen that there is an extraordinary order in the matters of nutrition, communication and reproduction of every living being. However, the purposefulness of the body structure is not only demonstrated in organisms with a higher organization, but covers the entire living world from head to toe right up to the most elementary forms of life, which is a necessary property of every living organism, but when there is no living body, there is no guarantee of purpose (purposefulness). It will not exist in natural conditions. Purposefulness in living organisms is accepted by the majority of biologists and scientists, and the only difference between the proponents of evolutionary theories is that they interpret purposefulness differently. According to Aparin, they use the purposeful evolutionary hypothesis and consider it as the result of natural selection presented by Darwin, and in other words, they think that the usefulness of an organ is the result of natural selection, while the supporters of the theory of creation or purposeful creation consider it to be the result of creation, and in other words, Others present it as the result of the implementation of the creator's previous plan.

Lamarckism:

Lamarck's opinion can be summarized as follows:

The use or non-use of organs under the influence of environmental conditions due to the animal's needs and the inheritance of acquired traits has caused animals to gradually adapt to different living environments. With the accumulation of these changes and their inheritance, new species appear. For example, Lamarck believed that the ancestors of the giraffe once had to feed on the leaves of the trees due to the lack of grass, so they tried to bring their heads closer to the leaves of the trees, and in this way, the muscles of the neck became longer due to more use and gradually Long necks have appeared in successive generations. Lengthening of the neck,

which is an acquired trait, has been gradually inherited from short-necked ancestors, and long necks have appeared, in the same way as Lamarck, the production of feathers between the toes of blue birds, or the loss of teeth in some Explains mammals.

The process of evolution in Lamarckism and Darwinism; Similarities and differences

According to the popular belief, one of the main axes of Lamarck's theory of evolution is the inheritance of acquired characteristics, and there are contradictory evidences against it that invalidate it. This article explains that, contrary to popular belief, the inheritance of acquired characteristics is not unique to Lamarck, but is one of the theoretical similarities between Lamarck and Darwin, and it seems that the evidence of the violation presented can be resolved. This study shows that the important differences in the views of these two founders of the theory of evolution are in their claims regarding the speed of evolution and the adoption of an individual or population approach to evolution and its purposefulness or randomness. Based on these similarities and differences, the present analysis explains that not only the pseudo-scientific nature of Lamarckian evolutionary theories is not acceptable, but maintaining the explanatory framework of Lamarckian is necessary for a more accurate understanding of the evolutionary process and in a way it can complement the Darwinian and neo-Darwinian narrative of evolution and use these two systems. A theory as a complement will increase the explanatory power of evolutionary theories.

Charles Robert Darwin (born February 12, 1809, England - died April 19, 1882, England) was an English biologist and geologist who is best known for his discoveries in the field of evolutionary science. His theory says that all species have a common ancestry. Today, this theory is accepted among scientists and is considered one of the fundamental concepts of biology, and of course, the influence of this theory is never limited to biology and has affected other fields of science. Darwin first proposed his theory that this evolution was the result of a process called natural selection, in which the effort to survive has a similar effect on selective

breeding in selective breeding in a joint article with Alfred Russel Wallace. Darwin is known as one of the most important people in human history. Also, his book *Origin of Species* is known as one of the most important scientific books in history.

In 1859, a year after publishing a joint paper with Wallace, Darwin published *On the Origin of Species*, in which he described his evidence for evolution; until the 1870s, evolution was accepted as a "truth" among the educated class. However, after the introduction of the modern synthesis in the early 20th century, a consensus emerged among scientists and natural selection was accepted as the basis of the mechanism of evolution. This scientific discovery of Darwin, while linking all biological sciences together, also explains biodiversity.

From childhood to university

Both families were largely Unitarian Christians, although the Wedgwoods had accepted Anglicans among themselves. Robert Darwin, himself a rather liberal, took his son Charles to be baptized at St. Chad Anglican's Church, Rushbury, in November 1809, but Charles and his siblings attended the Unitarian Church with their mother. By 1817, the eight-year-old Charles was interested in and collecting natural history before joining a day school run by his church preacher. His mother died in July of the same year. From September 1818 he joined his older brother Erasmus at the Anglican boarding school in the neighboring town of Shrewsbury.

In October 1825, after spending a year as an apprentice with his father, Darwin, along with his brother Erasmus, went to study at the University of Edinburgh Medical School (which was the best medical school in England at the time). But the brutality of the surgery led him to abandon medical studies and instead learn taxidermy from a freed black slave named John Edmondston, who had accompanied Charles Waterton through the rainforests of South America, in approximately 40 one-hour sessions a day.

In his second year at Charles University, he joined the Plinian Society, a natural history student group. In this group, radical democratic students with materialistic views challenged popular religious concepts of science. Darwin assisted Robert Edmund Grant in his research into the anatomy and life cycle of marine invertebrates in the Forth. On March 27, 1827, he presented his findings to Pliny that the black eggs found in wrinkled oyster shells were skate leech eggs. Grant once praised

Lamarck's evolutionary ideas. Darwin was surprised by Grant's boldness, but he had recently read similar ideas in the notes of his grandfather, Erasmus. Darwin was tired of the natural history lecture given by Robert Jameson. Jameson's geology course included a discussion between Neptunism and Plutonism. Darwin learned the taxonomy of plants and contributed to the collection of the University Museum - which at the time was one of the largest museums in Europe. - It would help.

In 1825, Darwin resented his father's refusal to study medicine, and he resolutely sent Charles to Christ's College, Cambridge, to obtain a bachelor's degree as the first step to becoming an Anglican priest. Since Darwin could not pass the final exam, he joined the regular course in January 1828. He preferred riding and shooting to reading. His cousin William Darwin Fox introduced him as a lover and crazy collector of beetles; Darwin pursued this work avidly, some of his findings being published in James Francis Stephens' *Sketches of British Insects*. Darwin became a close friend and follower of Botany Professor John Stevens Henslowe and met other prominent naturalist clergy. These clerics considered scientific work as natural religious theology. Darwin became known to students as "the man who walks with Henslow". Darwin devoted himself to studying when his exams were approaching, and the language and logic of William Paley's "Proof of Christianity" (1794) pleased him. Darwin performed well in his final exams in January 1831, placing 10th out of 178 candidates for the regular course.

Darwin in 1880

Darwin had to stay in Cambridge until June 1831. He read William Paley's *Natural Theology, or Proofs of the Existence of God and His Attributes* (first published in 1802), which led to the discussion of a divine design in nature, explaining that the consistency of God's action through laws is natural. He read John Herschel's new book *Preliminary Discourses on the Study of Natural Philosophy* (1831). This book described the highest goal of natural philosophy to understand such laws by induction and based on observation. Darwin also read Alexander von Humboldt's *Personal Narrative of Scientific Travels between 1799 and 1804*. Darwin was inspired by Humboldt with "burning enthusiasm" and planned to visit Tenerife with some of his classmates after graduation and study natural history in the tropics. To prepare, he attended Adam Sedgwick's geology course, and then on 4 August went with him on a two-week trip to map the Welsh strata.

Traveling with a beagle

After leaving Sedgwick in Wales, Darwin spent a week with his student friends at Barmouth, and then returned home on 29 August to find a letter from Henslow offering him a position as a naturalist (albeit an incomplete one) on board at his own expense. HMS Beagle Captain Robert FitzRoy was to accompany, emphasizing that this was a gentleman's occasion and not a "mere collector". The ship went on a voyage of discovery for four weeks to map the coast of South America. Robert Darwin objected to his son's planned two-year voyage as a waste of time, but his brother-in-law Josiah Wedgwood II convinced him to agree and pay for his son's participation. Darwin was careful to keep his work private so he could keep control of his collection, intending to keep it for a large scientific institution.

After some delays, the journey by ship started on December 27, 1831 and took five years. As Fitzroy had requested, Darwin spent most of this time on land conducting geological surveys, examining fossils, and studying animals, while the Beagle surveyed and mapped the coast. Darwin took careful notes of his observations and theories, and at intervals during his journey he sent his specimens with letters to Cambridge, including a copy of Beagle's Voyage to his family. He had some expertise in geology, collecting beetles, and dissecting marine invertebrates, but was otherwise a novice and skillfully collected specimens for expert evaluation. Despite the extreme discomfort of seasickness, Darwin wrote copious notes on the ship's deck. Most of his zoological notes were on marine invertebrates, beginning with plankton collected during the Pacific.

During his first stop on the coast of Santiago de Compostela, Cape Verde, Darwin noticed that the white bands on the volcanic rocks were sea snails. Fitzroy had given him the first volume of Charles Lyell's Principles of Geology, in which he explained the concepts of isotropism and the gradual changes of the Earth's surface over long periods of time. Darwin saw things Lyell's way and thought about theorizing and writing a book on geology. When they arrived in Brazil, Darwin was happy to see the tropical forests, but hated to see slavery, and argued with Fitzroy about it. Mapping continued in southern Patagonia. They stopped at Bahía Blanca, and on the rocks near Punta Alta Darwin discovered many fossilized bones of extinct mammals along with new seashells, indicating recent extinctions without any signs of climate change or natural disasters. He identified a lesser-known megadad by a

tooth and its association with bony armor, which he initially thought resembled a giant specimen of local armadillo armor. His findings attracted a lot of attention when they arrived in England.

On his horseback rides with the gauchos into the interior to explore the geology and collect more fossils, Darwin gained social, political, and anthropological insights into both the natives and the people living in the colonies at the time of the Revolution, and he noticed two types of hummingbirds occupying separate territories. But they have subscriptions. When they went further south, he saw plains that were terraced and made of rounded pebbles and sea snails and were higher than normal and showed a series of ridges. He read the second volume of Lyell's book and accepted his idea of "centers of creation" of species, but his own discoveries and theory challenged Lyell's ideas about the slow and gradual extinction of species.

Three Fuji natives had been taken on board the Beagle's maiden voyage, then trained as missionaries during a year's stay in England. Darwin found their behavior friendly and themselves civilized, yet in Tierra del Fuego he encountered wretched and despicable savages who were wilder than domestic animals. He was convinced that, despite their diversity, all human beings were related by a common origin and had the potential to evolve and become civilized. Unlike his scientist friends, he now believed that there was no impassable divide between man and beast. Abandoned after a year's mission, the three people from Fuji, who were called Jimmy Buttons, lived like natives, had wives, and did not want to return to England.

Darwin experienced an earthquake in Chile and saw signs of uplift, including a bed of black clams resting on the highest waves. d. On top of the Andes mountains he observed sea snails and several fossils of trees that grew on sandy beaches. He theorized that as the Earth rose, oceanic islands sank and coral reefs grew around them, forming ring reefs.

In the geology of the New Galapagos Islands, Darwin looked for evidence to connect the wildlife to the old "Creation Center" theory, and found that mockingbirds were related to those in Chile but varied from island to island. He had heard that slight changes in the shape of the turtles' shell would indicate which island they belonged to, but he was unable to collect them even after eating edible turtles as food. In Australia, marsupial kangaroos and duckbills looked so unusual that Darwin thought the two creatures were almost distinct. He found the Australian Aborigines

humorous and happy, and pointed out that their population had been decimated by European settlers.

Fitzroy investigated how the ringed hydroliths of the Cocos Islands formed, and his findings confirmed Darwin's theory. Fitzroy started to write a book of Beagle travel stories and after reading Darwin's memoirs, he suggested that he also publish them. Finally, Darwin's Beagle travel book was rewritten in a separate third volume of the ship travel memoirs.

In Cape Town, Darwin and Fitzroy met John Herschel, who had recently written to Lyell, praising his theory of homotheism, calling it an opening to bold speculations about "that secret of secrets," the replacement of extinct species by other species as a natural method of comparison. with a miraculous process. As the ship was returning home and he was sorting through his notes, Darwin wrote: "If my growing suspicions about mockingbirds, turtles, and the Falkland Island wolf are correct, such facts will undermine the theory of the fixation of species, and then before weakening with He added caution. Then he wrote: I think such facts shed light on the origin of species.

The beginning of Darwin's theory of evolution

By the time the ship arrived at Falmouth, Cornwall, on October 2, 1836, it was almost as famous in scientific circles as John Stevens Henslow had spread the fame of his former pupil by giving selected naturalists Darwin's geological pamphlets in December 1835. Darwin went to his home in Sherbury and saw his relatives, then hurried to Cambridge to see Henslow, who advised him to find naturalists to catalog the collection he had collected and agreed to do so for the plant species. . Darwin's father arranged for the investment so that his son could become an independent scientist, and Darwin excitedly and proudly visited institutions around London to find experts to describe his collections. Zoologists were working very late and it was feared that many specimens would remain in storage.

An enthusiastic Charles Lyell met Darwin for the first time on October 29, and soon introduced him to the budding anatomist Richard Owen. Owen used the facilities of the Royal College of Surgeons of England to work with the fossil bones that Darwin had collected. He was surprised to find that the fossils belonged to extinct species. Giant creatures such as ground sloths and megadeads, the fossils included a nearly

complete skeleton of Scleduterium and a skull the size of a hippopotamus, similar to a rodent called a bowtooth, and similar to a leaf-eating giant. The skeletal fragments were, as Darwin first thought, really belonged to a sloth, a huge armadillo-like creature. These extinct creatures were related to living species in South America. In mid-December, Darwin took up residence in Cambridge to organize work on his collections and review his travel notes. In his first letter he presented evidence of the uplift of a large area of South American land, and with Lyell's enthusiastic support, he read it to the Geological Society of London on January 4, 1837. On the same day, he exhibited the mammal and bird species of his collection at the Geological Society of London. In a short time, the ornithologist John Gould announced that the Galapagos birds, which Darwin thought were a mixture of the black toca, the red-breasted and the nightingale, were actually twelve different species of finch. On 17 February Darwin was elected to the Council of the Geological Society, and Lyell devoted his speech as President of the Geological Society to Richard Owen's findings on Darwin's fossil collection, emphasizing that the geographical continuity of the species supported his theories of homogeneity.

In early March, Darwin moved to London to be near his work. Darwin joined Lyell's social circle of scientists and experts like Charles Babbage, who described God as the planner of laws. Darwin remained part of the Whig Party circle with his free-thinking brother Erasmus and a close friend of the writer Harriet Martineau. Based on the Whig's controversial Poor Law Reform Act, Martineau promoted Malthusianism, which believed that population growth would lead to more poverty and the cessation of prosperity. As a Unitarian, Martineau was also interested in the radical consequences of species transplantation, which was influenced by Grant and the younger surgeons of Geoffroy. He said he was promoted. Trajesh was condemned by Orderly Anglicans, but famous scholars discussed the matter openly and openly, and there was widespread interest in John Herschel's letter. In his letter, Herschel admired Lyell's approach and saw it as a way to find the natural cause of the origin of new species.

Gould met Darwin and told him that the mockingbirds of the Galapagos Island were not a species of mockingbird, but a separate and different species from the birds of other islands, and that the bird that Darwin thought was an elic was in the finch group. Darwin He did not name the finches after the islands where they lived, but based on the notes of others on the ship, including Fitzroy, he assigned the names

of the islands to the species. The two rheas were distinct species, and on March 14 Darwin noted how their distribution changed as they moved south.

The emergence of the theory of evolution

At first, Darwin did not seek to challenge the hypothesis of the stability of species in any way, but the continuation of the research left many unanswered questions in front of him. A year before the start of the journey, a controversial book by Charles Lyell called "Principles of Geology" had been published, and Darwin had a copy of it with him. In this book, the author claimed that the surface of the earth changes due to gradual processes, and the transformation of the earth's crust is a uniform flow in nature throughout the history of this planet. He explains that every type of living thing first grows in a center and is spread from that point, and he showed that it lasted for a while until it gradually disappeared and gave its place to other species, and he calls it the principle of the centers of creation. Therefore, he concluded that the emergence of new species is a continuous and uniform flow throughout the history of the earth. These theories, which were completely contrary to the popular beliefs of the time, caused a lot of noise in scientific circles. By examining rock layers and fossils in different places, Darwin found many evidences in support of Lyle's theories. In the Galapagos Islands he found fossils very close but not quite identical to living forms. He observed that the turtles living in each island are slightly different from the turtles of the neighboring island and the turtles of different islands are slightly different from each other. According to Darwin, the best explanation was that species change and members of each species share a common ancestor.

Forty years before him, a scientist named Thomas Malthus had claimed in an article that the growth rate of the human population is higher than the amount of food production and if the human population is not controlled in some way, after a few decades there will not be enough food for everyone and people will have to Darwin found that Malthus's teachings complemented his ideas. He concluded that after changes are made in living organisms, species that have become incompatible with the natural environment are eliminated and species whose changes have made them more compatible with the natural environment take their place. Darwin called this phenomenon natural selection. From 1836 to 1858, Darwin secretly worked on his revolutionary theory in his spare time. He was already convinced of the existence of

the evolution of living things, but he was afraid that by making it public, he would be accused of blasphemy by radical groups. He, who knew what controversy would arise in society and scientific circles when his theory was presented, tried to provide sufficient and scientific evidence for his theory by conducting many experiments on plants and animals and using the experiences of pigeon and pig breeders.

Presenting the theory of evolution

Darwin's research progressed slowly. In 1842 he wrote a summary of his theory and in 1844 he wrote a 240-page treatise on natural selection. Despite the insistence of his friends, he was still hesitant to widely publish his ideas and shared the results of his research only with some of his close colleagues such as Charles Lyle and Joseph Dalton Hooker; But receiving a letter in June 1858 made Darwin put aside his doubts. The author of the letter was a young biologist named Alfred Russell Wallace who was working in Borneo. He also reached the same thoughts as Darwin about evolution. Darwin prepared a paper within two weeks and sent it to the Linnean Scientific Society along with Wallace's paper. His friends arranged for both articles to be published together, but together with documents proving Darwin's right of precedence. Darwin, whose will was stimulated by the awareness of the existence of competition, after presenting the paper, began to write a book entitled "On the origin of species by means of natural selection, or the survival of the fittest races in the struggle for existence." In this book, which later became known as "The Beginning of Species", he tried to explain the theory of evolution by natural selection and provide scientific evidence for it.

Darwin-Wallace theory

The Darwin-Wallace theory is based on three observations and two general results from these observations.

- Observation: If there is no environmental resistance, any type of organism increases according to the rule of geometric progression. In other words, a population that doubles its population in the first year can potentially quadruple in the second year and eightfold in the third year.
- Observation: But in nature, although there are sometimes changes in the size of the population of species, the size of the population of any species of living things remains constant during a long period of time.

Conclusion: It is clear that not all gametes become zygotes, not all zygotes become adults and not all adults remain and reproduce; Therefore, there must be a struggle for survival.

- Observation: All people are not the same type of living being, but they show major individual differences from each other.

Conclusion: Therefore, in the struggle for survival, individuals with more favorable differences will have an advantage in competition with others. So more of them will remain and produce more children.

As can be seen, Darwin and Wallace considered the environment as the main cause of natural selection, that is, the environment gradually destroys organisms with incompatible characteristics and preserves organisms with compatible characteristics. After the passage of many successive generations and the continuous effect of natural selection, finally a living group will develop a characteristic or a number of new and compatible characteristics to such a degree that it will emerge as a new species from the ancestral species.

Charles Darwin's religious view

As a teenager, Charles Darwin went to Cambridge University with the goal of becoming an Anglican clergyman. But gradually he lost his religious beliefs. He has given some of his opinions in his autobiography. Darwin writes on pages 85 and 87 of his book: "I deserve to be known as a theist. This conclusion has been on my mind for as long as I can remember when I was writing *The Origin of Species*. And gradually as I finished the book, this conclusion became weaker and weaker in me." Darwin continues: "But I was not at all eager to lose my belief, with so much disbelief it overcame me until it took over my whole being. This evolution happened so slowly that I never felt for a moment that I had made the wrong decision. In fact, I don't really understand why a person should wish that Christianity is true, apparently according to the clear advice of the text [the Bible], it should be said that people who do not believe, including my father, my brother and almost all my friends, should be punished for eternity. turn around And so such a doctrine is an abominable doctrine. However, he wrote in a letter to a friend in 1879: "In my most extreme swings, I have never been an atheist in the sense of denying the existence

of God. "I think generally and as I get older, but not always, the word agnostic gives a more accurate description of my state of mind."

From his animal breeding experiments and observation of nature, Darwin realized that more offspring were produced than survived. This was true of plants and animals from trees to elephants and everything in between. Some animals produce millions of eggs with thousands of larvae, and some plants produce millions of spores or seeds, but fortunately the great majority of this extra reproduction does not reach maturity.

Darwin's power of patient and careful insight led to the recognition that there are differences in nature. No two individuals are the same in puppies, baby carp, sticklebacks or foxes. The germination of the seeds of a plant produces different seedlings. Darwin's genius was to understand that this extra reproduction was related to differences. Finally, he came to the conclusion that there is competition for resources in nature, and that the differences that are best adapted to their environment exclude those who are less adapted. Since the environment does this selection, he called it natural selection against artificial selection carried out by breeders. This process leads to fission with change, which was his definition of evolution. Today, the knowledge of genetics, which was unknown in Darwin's time, is used to understand how this process works. Divergence with variation can be described as a change in gene frequency, a change in the proportion of an altered gene among all other possible forms of the same gene. Natural selection is differential reproduction. In other words, in an environment, one form leaves more descendants than other forms. Environment is the selecting factor.

Darwin had no idea of the source of these changes, and there was no way for him to know that the changes he observed in his animal breeding experiments were chemical mistakes, or sudden hereditary changes in a gene (mutations). In short, evolution is the divergence with change (change in the sequence of genes) that occurs as a result of natural selection (differential reproduction), and it acts on the changes that have been created as a result of mutation and other factors, while the environment It does the work of natural selection.

Genetic proof of evolution

Today, with the advancement of genetic science and biotechnology, the ability to compare the DNA of people and organisms through molecular markers has been provided. This capability is used to identify the kinship and similarity of organisms with each other, as well as for criminology and to distinguish between parents and children in judicial and legal matters; DNA testing has shown that the difference between human and chimpanzee DNA is about one percent, and this is a confirmation of the theory of evolution.

The reason for the objections

According to James Watson in the introduction of his book *Molecular Genetics*, despite the opposition, the theory of evolution was proven in the 1860s, but many continued to strongly oppose it, saying that their opposition was not based on science and was based on prejudices and religious beliefs.

Unscientific use of his theories

Darwin's theory has been used in cases where he himself undoubtedly disliked such interpretations. One of these cases is fascism's use of the idea of natural selection and survival of the fittest to prove the superiority of some races. In the same way, war between ethnic groups is also supported from the point of view that the weak are destroyed and their place is given to the strong. Marxists also distorted Darwinism to justify class struggles. The big economic companies also had no mercy and compassion in their way of working, and they saw Darwinism as a phenomenon that destroys small companies in a land in favor of big companies. Evolution means the change in the hereditary characteristics of living things during successive generations. [1][2][3] Evolution means that all living things, with all their diversity, come from a common ancestor that lived about 3.5 to 3.8 billion years ago. have appeared.

The scientific study of evolution began in the mid-nineteenth century, when research on fossils and the diversity of living things convinced many scientists that all living things must have evolved in some way. The mechanisms driving evolution remained unclear until the middle of the 19th century, the scientific theory of "evolution based on natural selection" was proposed by Charles Darwin and Alfred Russel Wallace, which explained how and why evolution occurs. In short, this scientific theory stated that only a generation of living beings have the ability to survive and reproduce,

which, due to genetic mutations, have gained more harmony with the changes in their living environment.

Evolution is the cause of the phenomenon of speciation; during which a single ancestral species splits into two or more different species. speciation in the structural, embryonic and genetic similarities of organisms; The geographical distribution of related species, and the fossil record of changes are visible. The common ancestor of today's living beings until more than 3.5 billion years ago; That is, it dates back to the time when life appeared on earth. Evolution occurs in various ways, both within a population and as speciation between populations; Slowly and continuously called cumulative selection, or quickly from one stationary position to the next position; which is called point balance.

In the early 20th century, the "theory of evolution based on natural selection" was integrated with genetics, paleontology, and systematics, which was joined by later findings such as molecular biology; It reached its peak under the title of modern synthesis. This combination became a major foundation in biology; As it provided a coherent and integrated explanation for biodiversity and the history of life on earth. Today, evolution is studied in various branches of biological sciences, such as survival biology, embryology, ecology, physiology, paleontology, agriculture, and medicine. Also, evolution has had an effect on other fields of human studies, such as anthropology, philosophy and psychology. evolution; It is the dominant example and the main framework of modern biology and forms its foundation and is supported by many evidences.

Terminology

Evolution was originally called "evolution". The Arabic word "evolution" means "completion". Dekhoda dictionary mentions its meaning as "finish". But because the word "evolution" evokes "to reach perfection" in the mind of the audience, many people are against using this word for Evolution. [16] This word was first used by the translators of the Qajar period as the Persian equivalent of the word "evolution" in European languages. . This is while the word Evolution means "emergence" and "transformation" and refers to the emergence of something from another thing. The word Evolution does not indicate the "perfecting" of living things. This word does not have any moral burden, but only shows the change of living things to adapt and adapt more to the environment, because in one environment, certain characteristics

are considered the basis of adaptation and adaptation, and in another environment, other characteristics. Although the word "evolution" has an Arabic origin, the Arabic speakers themselves use the word "tawhur" (meaning change). Fargasht is a derived noun, consisting of: "Far" (forward prefix) + Gesht (to turn and transform); Therefore, the word evolution is a more appropriate equivalent for Evolution.

"Farghest" is one of the creations of Farhangistan II. [18] This word is used in the works of writers such as Dariush Ashouri. Later, other equivalents were suggested by Persian-speaking researchers for Evolution; Among them is the word "Baraish" which was proposed by Ebrahim Herandi, a psychologist. In Persian-language sources and media, instead of the word evolution, words such as "progress" and "improvement" have been used, and in some scientific programs broadcast by the Islamic Republic of Iran Radio and Television, the phrase "adaptation and change" has also been used. In Urdu and Sindhi language, which are languages of the same root and family with Persian language, This theory of "improvement" is said and written.

History of evolutionary thought

For more details on this section, see History of evolutionary thought.

ancient votes

The suggestion that one species of animal may have originated from another species is seen in the opinions of some pre-Socratic philosophers such as Anaximander and Empedocles. In contrast to these materialist views, Aristotle considered all natural objects and not only living beings to be incomplete acts of possible natural states; which were fixed. He called these fixed states, form or example; or (in Latin translation) called species. This view was part of Aristotle's divine understanding of nature, in which all objects played an ultimate role in the divine system of the world. Of course, he did not claim that every animal has a one-to-one correspondence with a specific metaphysical form; Rather, he mentioned examples of how new species of living things could have arisen. Various interpretations of Aristotle's theory, after combining with Christian teachings, became the conventional understanding in the Middle Ages.

17th and 18th centuries

In the 17th century, the new method of modern science rejected the Aristotelian approach to nature, and sought to explain natural phenomena in the form of natural laws; which were the same for all sensations, without the assumption of any fixed natural order or divine system of the world. But this new approach slowly took root in biology; which became the last bastion for a stable understanding of natural objects.

John Ray used the term species, which was abandoned at that time, to refer to fixed types of animals and plants; But unlike Aristotle, he strictly introduced each type of living being as a species. Ray proposed that each species can be recognized by the characteristics that remain and maintain themselves in each generation. These species were designed by God; But they showed differences that emerged due to local conditions. In the biological classification of organisms by Carl Linnaeus, which was introduced in 1735; Species were considered fixed based on divine design.

Some other naturalists of this time speculated about the evolutionary changes of species based on the laws of nature. In 1751, Maupertoi wrote about the changes that occur during reproduction; And he considered the accumulation of these changes over generations as the driving force of evolution. Buffon suggested that species might be decomposed into multiple organisms; And Erasmus Darwin hypothesized that all warm-blooded animals may have been derived from a single microbe (or, as he called it, from a single filament).

Lamarck's Theory: Substantial Transformation

The first mature evolutionary plan was Jean Lamarck's "transmutation" theory, which was published in 1809 in the book *Philosophy of Zoology*. Lamarck envisioned that as spontaneous generation continued to produce simpler forms of life; Further complexity develops in parallel lineages with an inherited progressive tendency. So that the heritable changes due to the use or non-use of the parents lead the lineages to compromise more with the environment.[24][25] This proposed process was later called Lamarckism. The camp of naturalists condemned these opinions due to the lack of empirical evidence. Cuvier emphasized that species are unrelated and fixed; And their similarities indicate the divine design and based on their functional needs.

At the same time, the idea of the benevolent designer John Ray; It was developed by William Paley in the direction of natural theology. Paley argued that the complex arrangements of living organisms are signs of divine design. The young Charles Darwin admired Paley's opinions.

Darwin's Theory: Natural Selection

Charles Darwin's theory of evolution is considered a turning point in the issue of proof or evolution of species. Darwin influenced by the opinions of Thomas Malthus in his treatise Principle of Population; concluded that population growth can easily lead to a "survival conflict"; And in this competition, those born with more desirability will have an advantage over others. Resource limitation causes many offspring to die before reaching reproductive age in each generation. This idea could explain the diversity of animals and plants, while deriving from common ancestors; And at the same time, this explanation was provided only by using natural laws that were the same for all objects.

Darwin achieved the theory of natural selection in 1838, but did not publish it; Until in 1858, he received a letter from a young biologist named Alfred Wallace, in which a similar theory was described. In this letter, Wallace asked Darwin for help in publishing his hypothesis. They submitted two separate papers to be read at a scientific meeting of the Linnaean Society in London.

Neither Darwin nor Wallace attended the meeting, and at the time few people knew about the two papers. Finally, at the end of 1859, Darwin's book called "On the Origin of Species by Means of Natural Selection" was published and he devoted himself to describing Darwinian evolution. Thomas Huxley used comparative anatomy and paleontology to show that humans and apes shared a common ancestor. This implied conclusion that man does not have a unique and special place in the world, upset many.

The birth and development of genetic knowledge

The exact mechanisms of inheritance, and the origin of new traits, remained enigmatic. To solve this puzzle, Darwin proposed the theory of pangenesis. [39] In 1865, Gregor Mendel reported that phenotypic characteristics are inherited in a predictable pattern resulting from the independent segregation and fusion of a number of elements. (These elements were later called genes) Mendelian laws of

inheritance finally rejected Darwin's theory of pangenesis. August Weisman made an important distinction between germinal (sperm and egg) and somatic (body) cells of the body; And made it clear that inheritance is only through the germline It works. Hugo Devory related Darwin's theory of pangenesis with Weisman's somagerminal differentiation and proposed the hypothesis that the effect of pangenes, which are concentrated in the cell nucleus, is transferred to the cytoplasm by expression and changes the structure of the cell. Devory also believed that the transmission of diverse traits to offspring through the germline was done through Mendelian inheritance. [41] In explaining the origin of new characteristics, Devory developed the mutation hypothesis, which led to a temporary disagreement between scientists who believed in Darwinian evolution, and Their biometer was followed by Duvvari. At the beginning of the 20th century, the pioneers of population genetics such as John Haldin, Saal Wright, and Ronald Fisher provided a solid and computational basis for evolution; And the apparent contradiction between Darwin's theory, genetic mutations and Mendelian inheritance disappeared.

Modern synthesis

In the 1920s and 1930s, the Modern Synthesis linked the Mendelian concepts of natural selection, mutation, and heredity into a unified theory that is generally applicable to all branches of the biological sciences. The new evolutionary synthesis was able to explain observed patterns in species and populations, fossil changes in paleontology, and even complex cellular mechanisms in embryology.

Recent developments

In 1953, James Watson and Francis Crick, by discovering the structure of the DNA molecule, provided a detailed basis for explaining its activities. Molecular biology has improved our understanding of the relationships between genotype and phenotype. Advances in phylogenetics and systematics, through the publication and use of evolutionary trees, mapped the evolution of traits in a comparative and testable framework. In 1973, evolutionary biologist Theodosius Dobzhansky wrote, "Nothing in biology makes sense except in the light of evolution," because evolution brings together things that once seemed unrelated; It takes place in the form of a coherent description that is able to describe and predict the observed facts about life.

Since then, the new evolutionary synthesis has expanded to explain the scale of biological organization, from gene to species. This extension is called Eco-Evo-Devo.

The role of heredity in the evolution of traits

According to Biddle and Tatum's 1940 theory called "one gene-one enzyme theory", each gene has the code to make one enzyme. Today, this theory has been corrected as "one gene-one polypeptide theory". The evolutionary result of heredity is that genes carry the code for building proteins, and proteins are responsible for embryonic and postnatal reactions affecting the structural, physiological, biochemical and behavioral traits (in the case of brain cells) of organisms. These traits affect the chances of survival and reproduction to different degrees; And as a result, the frequency of alleles changes over many generations.

Lamarck's theory of evolution was rejected for a long time due to the rejection of the inheritance of acquired traits; Despite these findings of the last few decades, they have shown that some acquired traits can be inherited without changing the sequence of DNA nucleotides. The mechanisms of this type of inheritance such as DNA methylation, gene silencing through RNA interference, and the third protein structure in prions; All of them are classified under epigenetic inheritance and play a role in evolution. Also, except epigenetic inheritance; Other types of inheritance also participate in evolution, which are not directly under the control of genes, and among them, DIT and symbiosis can be mentioned.

Natural selection

For more details on this section, see Natural Selection.

Evolution by natural selection is the process by which genetic mutations that improve survival and reproduction become more common in a population; And they remain a population in successful generations. This mechanism is often called "obvious"; Because it necessarily follows the following three simple facts:

- There are genetic variations within every population of living beings.
- Organisms produce more offspring than they can survive.
- These children differ in their ability to survive and reproduce.

Such a situation leads to the formation of competition between organisms for survival and reproduction; As a result, organisms whose inherited characteristics give them an advantage over competitors pass these beneficial characteristics on to the next generation; While the non-useful features do not reach the next generation.

The central concept in natural selection is the concept of organismic organization. Adaptability is measured by the ability to survive and reproduce, which determines its participation in the next generation. Compatibility not with the total number of births, but with a proportion of subsequent generations that carry living genes; is determined. For example, an organism that survives well and reproduces quickly, but leaves small and weak offspring; It will have negligible genetic contribution in subsequent generations, and thus its fitness is considered low.

Consequences

Evolution affects every aspect of the form and behavior of living things. Most prominent are the specific behavioral and physical adaptations that result from natural selection. These compromises with the help of activities such as finding food, avoiding predators or attracting mates; They increase fitness. Organisms can also help their relatives or participate in mutually beneficial symbiosis; Answer the choice. In the long run, evolution splits ancestral populations into new species that do not interbreed.

These consequences of evolution are sometimes divided into macro-evolution and micro-evolution. Macroevolution occurs at the species level or above species, such as extinction and speciation; Whereas microevolution involves smaller changes such as adaptations within a species or population. In general, macroevolution is considered as the long-term result of microevolution. ; Therefore, the distinction between micro and macro evolution is not fundamental, it is caused by the effect of time. Although in macroevolution the traits of all species may be important. For example, a large amount of variation among individuals allows a species to quickly adapt to new habitats, reducing the chance of extinction, while a wide geographic range increases the chance of speciation, as it is more likely that part of the population Separated and isolated. In this sense, microevolution and macroevolution may involve different levels of selection - microevolution acts on genes and organisms, while macroevolutionary processes such as species selection affect the entire species and change the rate of speciation and extinction.

A common misconception is that evolution has long-term goals and plans, the reality is that evolution has no long-term goals and does not necessarily lead to greater complexity. Although complex species have evolved, they are seen as a side effect of the increase in the number of all living things, and simpler forms of life are still more abundant in the biosphere. The vast majority of species are microscopic prokaryotes, which despite their small size account for half of the biomass and the vast majority of Earth's biodiversity. Simple organisms are the dominant form of life on earth throughout the history of life and up to the present day; Complex life is more remarkable only because it seems more varied. In fact, the evolution of microorganisms is particularly important in modern evolutionary research, because their rapid reproduction makes it possible to study experimental evolution, and to observe evolution and adaptation in short periods of time.

co-evolution

The interaction of organisms can create both incompatibility and cooperation. Whenever the interaction is between a pair of species, for example between pathogen and host or between predator and prey, corresponding sets of adaptations develop. So that the evolution of one species causes compromises in the second species. These changes in the second species, in turn, create new compromises in the first species. This cycle of selection and response is called coevolution.

Evolutionary cooperation

Not all evolutionary interactions between species involve conflict. Many things have evolved based on mutual benefits. For example, we can mention the strong cooperation between plants and mycorrhizal fungi.

speciation

See speciation for more details on this section.

Speciation is a process in which a species tends to two or more than two species. There are several ways to define the concept of "species". The choice of definition depends on the characteristics of the related species. For example, some species concepts are readily applied with regard to the sexual reproduction of living things; while others with regard to asexual reproduction. Despite the disagreement on the

concept of species, these different concepts can be included in one of the following three philosophical approaches: ecological, reproductive, or mating-based.

Extinction

For more details on this section, see Extinction.

Extinction is the complete disappearance of species. Extinction is not an uncommon event, as species regularly appear through speciation and disappear through extinction. Almost all animal and plant species that once lived on earth are now extinct; And extinction seems to be the ultimate fate of all species.

The evolutionary history of life

Genetic explanation of evolution

Today, with the advancement of genetic science and biotechnology, the ability to compare the DNA of people and organisms through molecular markers has been provided. This capability is used to identify the kinship and similarity of organisms with each other, as well as for criminology and to distinguish between parents and children in judicial and legal matters; DNA testing has shown that the difference between human and chimpanzee DNA is about one percent, and this is a confirmation of the theory of evolution.

Applications

For more details on this section, see Advanced Applications.

Concepts and models of evolution, like natural selection, have many applications.

Artificial selection is the deliberate selection of traits in a population of organisms. This is the same method that has been used to domesticate animals and plants for thousands of years. Artificial selection has become a vital part of genetic engineering today; For example, selective markers such as microbial resistance genes can be used to change DNA. Understanding the changes of organisms during evolution determines the genes responsible for actions and body structure; Genes that may be involved in human genetic disorders.

In computer science, the simulation of evolution started with the use of evolutionary algorithms and artificial life in the 1960s; and developed into artificial selection

simulation. As a result of Ingo Rechenberg's work, artificial selection is widely recognized as an optimization method. Rechenberg applied evolutionary strategies to solve complex engineering problems.

Opposition to evolution

Since the ideas of evolution were raised in the 19th century, oppositions to evolution were also raised. When Charles Darwin published his book titled *On the Origin of Species* in 1859, his theory of evolution first faced opposition from scientists with different theories; But finally it was universally approved in scientific circles. The most objections to evolution are expressed by those religious people who believe that species were created in six days and have been and will be constant from beginning to end.

The mentioned cases for rejection of evolution

Lack of observation

The common claim of creationists is that evolution has never been observed. Engaging with such objections often leads to debates over the definition of evolution. According to the conventional biological definition of evolution, observing the occurrence of evolution is a simple matter. Evolutionary processes, in the form of generation-to-generation changes in population genetic composition, have been observed in different scientific fields; including the evolution of fruit flies, mice, and bacteria in the laboratory. Such studies of *in vitro* evolution, especially those using microorganisms, provide an important understanding of how evolution occurs; Especially regarding antibiotic resistance.

In response to these examples, creationists specify that their objections only refer to macroorganisms, not microorganisms. Most creationist organizations do not deny the occurrence of short-term and relatively small evolutionary changes, which have even been observed in the development and breeding of dogs. Instead, creationists reject the occurrence of major evolutionary changes during the ages, which cannot be observed directly, and are only inferred from microevolutionary processes (microevolution) and the effects and signs of macroevolutionary processes (massive evolutionary change). According to the definition given by biologists of macroevolution, both microevolution and macroevolution have been observed. For example, speciation, contrary to popular misconception, has been observed many

times. In addition, today's evolutionary synthesis does not distinguish between macroevolution and microevolution in the processes described by evolutionary theory.

Transitional fossils also establish plausible links between several different groups of organisms; Like Archaeopteryx, which links birds with dinosaurs; or the tictalite, which links fish with limbed amphibians. Creationists reject these examples d; By saying that the fossils are a hoax, or that the fossils belong exclusively to one group or another, and by saying that there should be more evidence of transitional species. Darwin himself called the small number of transitional species one of the biggest weaknesses of his theory.

Darwin was fascinated by the limited collection of the time, the extremely long time involved, and the different rate and speed of change in some living species that differed little from Silurian fossils. In later revisions (in his book) he added: "The period during which the species have undergone change and transformation, though counted as a very long year, is probably compared with the period during which the same species have remained unchanged." It is short". The number of clear (and clean) transitional fossils has greatly increased compared to Darwin's time, and this problem has largely been resolved with the emergence of punctuated equilibrium theory. As more and more direct evidence accumulates for intermediate species (or intermediate species) and species-by-species evolution, creationists have redefined their understanding of the emergence of "created species or species," and have emphasized that a more effective demonstration and proof must be made of the form to be produced experimentally. A variant of this objection is the "were you there?", raised by "young earth creationist" Ken Ham. The objection is that since no one but God is able to directly observe events in the distant past, scientific claims are only speculation or storytelling. In fields such as astrophysics or meteorology, where direct observation or laboratory experiments are difficult or impossible, instead, the scientific method relies on observation and logical deduction. In these disciplines, the falsifiability test is used in such a way that a theory is used to predict the results of new observations. When such observations contradict the predictions of a theory, they may be reexamined or rejected if new, better explanations for the observed facts are substituted. For example, Newton's theory of gravity was replaced by Einstein's theory of general relativity, which more accurately predicted the orbit of Mercury.

Uncertain evidence

Illustrations of dog and human fetuses, which look almost identical up to four weeks. Presented by Haeckel in 1868 as evidence for evolution. One objection is that evolution is based on uncertain evidence, and it is claimed that evolution does not even have sufficient evidence. Generally, this objection is based on the argument that either the evidence of evolution is full of deception and deceitful jokes, and the current evidence of evolution is about to be discredited like some other evidence in the past, or that a certain number of evidences do not fit together and are suspect. Arguments against the certainty of evolution are mostly based on the analysis of the history of evolutionary thought or the history of science. Creationists point out that in the past, great scientific revolutions swept away theories that were considered almost certain at the time. This group claims that the current theory of evolution is likely to undergo a revolution in the future. It has also been claimed that some of the earlier evidence for evolution, now considered obsolete and fallacious, such as Ernst Haeckel's 19th-century comparative drawings of embryos to illustrate the theory of regeneration (or the course of evolution), were not only errors, but hoaxes. Molecular biologist Jonathan Wells criticizes biology textbooks for continuing to reproduce rejected evidence. In response, the National Center for Science Studies notes that none of the books reviewed by Wells contained the alleged errors; Because Haeckel's drawings are presented in a historical context with a discussion of why they are wrong, and the accurate modern day drawings and photographs in these books are rendered inappropriate and bad by Wells.

Uncertain chronology or chronology

Creationists claim that evolution relies on certain types of evidence that do not provide reliable information about the past. For example, it has been argued that radiometric dating (radiometric dating), as a technique for estimating the age of materials, is based on the fact that the rate of radioactive decay or radioactive decay of certain isotopes gives inconsistent and uncertain results. Especially, radiocarbon dating or radiocarbon dating based on carbon 14 isotope has been criticized. It is argued that radiometric decay relies on a number of unwarranted assumptions such as uniformitarianism. Such arguments have been dismissed by scientists who have confirmed the reliability of radiometric dating in its entirety by independent

methods. In addition, different methods and techniques of radiometric dating have confirmed each other's results independently.

Another form of objection is that the fossil evidence is unreliable. This case is based on a much broader range of claims, including many gaps in the fossil record; And fossil dating is a circular argument; Certain fossils, such as polystrata fossils, appear to have been displaced. The investigation of geologists considers the polystrat fossils to be compatible with the formation in the same place. That some features of evolution, instead of supporting the gradual equilibrium of evolution, which some consider to be a theory lacking in generalizability to explain gaps and intervals in the fossil record, supports the belief of creationists that the earth's crust underwent sudden revolutions of nature (compared to the heavenly calamity of the flood). huge).

Reasons of opposing scientists

Some scientists believe that Darwin's theory is not enough to explain human life and creation. "Darwinism was an interesting idea in the 19th century, but there are doubts about the ability of natural selection to create complex biological systems," says Colin Reeves of Coventry University. He is one of the scientists who declared his scientific opposition to Darwinism.

At a seminar on evolutionary morphology held at the University of Chicago on November 5, 1981, Colin Patterson spoke to more than fifty experts in related fields and guests from the American Museum of Natural History in New York, a historical presentation on this facial science. and the issue of not knowing Darwin's theory for sure was discussed. held another seminar at the American Museum of Natural History; In both of them, Colin Patterson first posed a question:

"Can you tell me anything you know about evolution, any one thing that is true"

At both seminar venues, no one could answer Colin Patterson's question, and his talk was welcomed by morphologists at the University of Chicago.

Jed Maksko, a molecular biologist at Berkeley University, says this about the rejection of the theory of evolution: There are about one hundred trillion cells in the human body, and each of them has a nucleus that contains DNA or genome. And each human genome has about 3 billion pieces of information; Each of those

sections can have four game combinations (A-T-G-S). So when you multiply those four combinations by 3 billion different pieces of information, the amount of information inside human cells is incredibly huge, and what really amazes me is that only a few combinations of those genomes have a huge probability ratio and combinations. The huge variety of DNA within the cell allows humans to perform their functions and maintain their stability.

Francis Crick, one of the discoverers of the DNA double helix and winner of the Nobel Prize in Physiology, states in his book that the building blocks of life must be the result of something more than random mutations. Crick risked his scientific credibility with this statement. He says: An honest man who is aware of all the existing knowledge can only say that In some cases, the origin of life is more like a miracle. He goes on to say, in the scientific world, this statement is equivalent to blasphemy (scientifically). I believe that something more than luck has led to our existence.

"Basically, natural selection has to find something that works at least a little bit, and then it gets modified a little bit, and it gets modified a little bit more in the next generation," says Michael Bihey, a biochemist at Lehigh University and the founder of the philosophy of irreducible complexity. He knew that if things were to evolve faster than usual or in too long a step, then one would suspect that something other than natural selection might have been at work. However, it is easy to point out structural defects such as irreducible complexity in many biological systems and show that natural selection has very, very large obstacles in these systems and it can be pointed out that scientists have not been able to use natural selection to explain such issues. . As a result, we have a lot of evidence that says that many biological systems in creation cannot have emerged with countless continuous and partial Darwinian modifications. Michael Bihi has mentioned these points in a documentary titled "Opening the Mystery of Life" and also in several scientific seminars held at Lehigh University.

Books and articles

Today, with the advancement of genetic science and biotechnology, the ability to compare the DNA of people and organisms through molecular markers has been provided. This capability is used to identify the kinship and similarities of beings with each other, as well as for criminology and to distinguish between parents and

children in judicial and legal matters; DNA testing has shown that the difference between human and chimpanzee DNA is about one percent, and this is a confirmation of the theory of evolution.

The reason for the objections

According to James Watson in the introduction of his book *Molecular Genetics*, despite the oppositions, the theory of evolution was proved in the 1860s, but many continued to strongly oppose it, saying that their oppositions were not based on science and were based on prejudices and religious beliefs. Furthermore, today, the overwhelming majority (nearly 97%) of the scientific community accepts evolution as the superior scientific theory in explaining the diversity of life, and the scientific community has decisively argued against and rejected the opponents' challenges.

Charles Darwin's religious views

Charles Darwin's views on religion have always been discussed. His works in the field of modern biology and the theory of evolution had a tremendous impact on the topics related to religion and science in his time. By the early 20th century, his views had become central to the creation versus evolution debate in the United States.

While Darwin strongly opposed the fanatical precepts of the Anglican Church and Christianity in general, he later made his position as an agnostic clear in response to a letter from John Fordyce:

"Even in the most intense turmoils of my life, I have never denied the existence of God and I have never been an atheist. I think generally (and more so as I get older) but not always, agnostic would be the most accurate description of my mindset and thoughts."

Charles Darwin had a religious background as a monotheistic Protestant who studied at an Anglican school. He went to Cambridge University for his undergraduate degree, which included studying Anglican theology, with the goal of becoming a priest. Darwin was very interested in natural history and according to John Herschel, he became interested in scientific topics by studying natural theology by William Paley. Natural theology, by presenting the argument of order (argument of divine design), tried to explain the category of consistency in nature by applying God's power through natural laws. Darwin remained orthodox on the Beagle's voyage,

looking for "centers of creation" to explain its distribution, and it was in the final stages of the voyage that he began to doubt the fixedness of species. During this period, Darwin criticized the Bible as a historical source and wondered why all religions should not be equally valid. After his return in October 1836, he developed his innovative ideas in the field of geology, while at the same time thinking about the transfer of species and religion.

Darwin's religious background

Charles Darwin was born during the Napoleonic Wars and grew up in the post-war era. During this period the government was dominated by conservatives close to the Anglican Church who suppressed radicalism. In his memoirs, he remembers the Enlightenment of the 18th century and the many and different interpretations that Protestant churches had of Christianity. Charles' extended family was a mixture of Whig-supporting Darwins and Wedgwoods, and was strongly monotheistic. Of course, one of his grandfathers, Erasmus Darwin, was a freethinker (his father was secretly a freethinker), but as a physician he avoided any social conflict with his Anglican supporters. While Darwin's parents agreed to baptize Charles in the Church of England in order to avoid social pressure, his religious mother took the children to a monotheist church. After his mother's death when he was only 8 years old, Darwin went to Shrewsbury boarding school.

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As Darwinian scholar Joseph Carroll of the University of Missouri–St. Louis puts it in his introduction to a modern reprint of Darwin's work: "The Origin of Species has special claims on our attention. It is one of the two or three most significant works of all time—one of those works that fundamentally and permanently alter our vision of the world...It is argued with a singularly rigorous consistency but it is also eloquent, imaginatively evocative, and rhetorically compelling." Carroll, Joseph, ed. (2003). On the origin of species by means of natural selection. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview. p. 15. ISBN 978-1-55111-337-1.

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GODMENT

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